

**CREATING SAFER HEALTHCARE THROUGH CARE GIVER EDUCATION: A
FOCUS ON WELLNESS, RESILIENCY, AND CULTURAL SAFETY WITHIN
HEALTH CARE ASSISTANT EDUCATION AT YUKON UNIVERSITY**

By

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Dedications

This project is dedicated to Elder Nina Bolton. The impact that you have on those around you and the community at large is profound. Thank you for taking this journey with me and sharing your knowledge and wisdom with me and so many others. I am forever grateful to have had the opportunity to learn from you and share in teaching others alongside you.

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Abstract

This project aimed to enhance the foundational knowledge and skills related to wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education for students in the Health Care Assistant (HCA) program at Yukon University. By revising the HCA 111 course, the project aimed to prepare students for success as front-line caregivers. Project objectives included conducting a literature review, engaging with Scandinavian colleges and universities, conversations with employed Yukon HCAs, consulting with local Indigenous knowledge holders on course revisions, and revising and delivering the course. This project addresses pressing needs in the Yukon healthcare system such as caregiver burnout and Indigenous-specific racism and discrimination. The revisions incorporated self-awareness learning, Elder-led learning, land-based learning, community experiential learning, and cultural safety education. The socio-ecological model and the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model guided the course revisions through a Two-Eyed Seeing approach in conjunction with cultural principles of meaningful relationships (9 Rs) and flexible content delivery to promote student wellness, resilience, and cultural safety. This project contributes to creating safer health care environments for both caregivers and Yukon Indigenous health care recipients.

Keywords: caregiver education, wellness, resiliency, cultural safety, Health Care Assistant, Yukon University, curriculum revision.

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Introduction

The purpose of this master's level project is to address caregiver burnout and Indigenous-specific racism and discrimination. This urgency to create safer health care environments necessitates the preparation of Health Care Assistant (HCA) students who possess deep self-awareness, enabling them to develop knowledge, skills, and attitudes foundational to wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education. By incorporating these vital concepts into the revisions of HCA 111, a lifestyle and choices course, students can create meaningful responses to the needs of Yukon Indigenous health care recipients and promote safe interactions within the healthcare system. Ultimately, this project seeks to promote a culturally safe, sustainable HCA workforce confronting the Yukon healthcare system.

Project Significance, Aims, and Positionality

This project centred on the revision of a first-level course within the HCA program at Yukon University that sought to provide students with enhanced foundational knowledge and skills related to wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education. The project sought to equip future front-line caregivers with deeper self-awareness that fosters meaningful responses to the needs of Yukon Indigenous health care recipients and promotes safe interactions within the healthcare system. The project is framed by the methodology of appreciative inquiry. Within the framework of appreciative inquiry, the specific course revisions are guided by the socio-ecological model, the First Nations Holistic Wellness Model, a Two-Eyed Seeing approach and cultural principles (9 Rs). These are combined with insights gleaned from an experiential trip to several Scandinavian universities as well as conversations with employed Yukon HCAs and a local First Nations Elder. Through the integration of self-awareness learning, Elder-led learning, land-based learning, community experiential learning, cultural safety education, and flexible

content delivery, HCA students are better prepared to maintain wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety in the Yukon healthcare system.

Project Significance

This project is inspired by my personal and professional experience of working within the healthcare system in the Yukon and my passion to see HCA's become safer health care providers. While I was in the third year of nursing school, I started work as an HCA in the Yukon. Then, upon graduation from the baccalaureate nursing program with the University of Northern British Columbia (UNBC), I started my nursing career in the Yukon. During my years as a health care provider, I have become increasingly aware of issues related to the resilience of health care workers, systemic challenges within the healthcare system, and a lack of the cultural awareness, safety, and understanding needed by providers to deliver high quality health services.

Throughout my nursing education, I learned about the importance of culture in health care and the unique needs of individuals from different backgrounds. However, I struggled to navigate the rigid rules and policies of the healthcare system, often unsure of what constituted appropriate care. As a young nurse in the hospital, I focused on providing the expected care; without fully considering the broader consequences of my actions. I found myself reciting discriminatory policies, rushing through discharge teaching, and leaving work emotionally distressed without knowing how to handle my feelings of anguish.

As the years went by and I moved between different healthcare settings, hoping to find a system in which patients felt genuinely cared for, I began to feel growing emotional distress. I listened intently to the stories of my patients, trying to understand what we were all missing in the healthcare system. It was during this time that I cared for a residential school survivor who, due to past experiences of racism and discrimination, refused to access formalized healthcare

structures. He wanted to be supported by those who truly cared about him while immersed in his culture rather than be confined within sterile buildings. I found that many patients expressed feelings of loneliness and isolation, teaching me that health care goes beyond mere knowledge and skill—it's about connecting with people on a human level.

As a registered nurse, I have had the honour of being a witness to the most vulnerable and powerful moments in people's lives, from the beginning to the end and everything in between. I learned that each of these moments carried value and cost. As a nurse, my actions had a direct impact on patients' experiences, their perception of health care, and their sense of safety during vulnerable times. I also discovered that caring for others impacted me deeply, both when I could provide excellent care and when I faced limitations in doing so. I experienced compassion fatigue and burnout while working within systems that didn't always meet people's needs in a meaningful way.

In 2018, I embarked on a new journey as an educator for HCA students at Yukon University. This experience ignited a passion within me to effect significant change in the lives of those I taught. I felt a deep sense of responsibility to prepare these students for the challenges they would encounter in health care, particularly in terms of the health, wellness, and cultural safety of Yukon First Nations people who have historically endured discrimination. My goal was to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to provide holistic care that respects cultural differences and fosters healing. Additionally, I recognized the importance of nurturing the well-being and resilience of care providers themselves in such a demanding environment.

During this period, I dedicated myself to deepening my understanding of working with Yukon First Nations people with the aim of ensuring that accessing healthcare is a safe and

healing experience rather than a harmful one. While I expanded my knowledge of Yukon First Nations culture and wisdom through education, experiences, conversations, and listening, I understood that collaborating with local indigenous knowledge holders would provide the most effective means of education to promote wellness, resilience, and culturally safe care within the HCA program at Yukon University.

Project Purpose and Aims

In 2020, I came across the *In Plain Sight: Addressing Indigenous-Specific Racism and Discrimination in BC Health Care* report, which sparked my interest in understanding how the Yukon was addressing systemic racism and cultural safety within its healthcare system (Turpel-Lafond, 2020). The report highlighted that only 16% of Indigenous patients *did not* experience discrimination when receiving health care (Turpel-Lafond, 2020). Discrimination, racism, and prejudice have detrimental effects on health and wellness, contributing to higher rates of suicidal ideation, substance use, and distress (Turpel-Lafond, 2020). Considering the Yukon's Indigenous population accounts for approximately 25% of the total population (Government of Yukon, 2023), compared with 5.9% of Indigenous individuals in British Columbia (Statistics Canada, 2017), I found that it was crucial to address the potential impact of discrimination on Indigenous individuals within the Yukon healthcare system. If the statistics from the *In Plain Sight* (Turpel-Lafond, 2020) report are expressed in the form of individuals affected in the Yukon, approximately 8,800 Yukon Indigenous people experience discrimination when receiving health care each year.

While I was investigating cultural safety in the Yukon, the COVID-19 pandemic was highlighting the strain on the healthcare system. I saw an opportunity to use my time in the Master of Science in Nursing program to gain a deeper understanding of health care worker

wellness and to explore how caregiver education could enhance health care safety for care providers and care recipients. My project sought to directly address the pressing issues of caregiver burnout, systemic racism, and discrimination, with a particular focus on Indigenous healthcare recipients in the Yukon. To address these objectives, I chose to address wellness, resilience, and cultural safety together.

While completing course work in the Master of Science in Nursing program at the University of Northern British Columbia, I focused on the concepts of mental wellness of post-secondary students and cultural safety in healthcare. As I studied these two concepts, I developed an understanding that self-awareness and personal resilience served as a foundational concept for both mental wellness of post-secondary students and cultural safety of caregivers. During a master's level course on health promotion, I came across the socio-ecological model within the 2020 Canadian National Standard for the Mental health and well-being of post-secondary students by the Canadian Standards Association (CSA Group, 2020). I was drawn to this model due to its holistic approach to promoting positive mental health and well-being among post-secondary students. While studying the socio-ecological model, I was reminded of the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model from the First Nations Health Authority of British Columbia which I had come across during a conference in 2018 (FNHA, 2017). As I examined these two models, I was struck by the similarities they shared in their approach to wellness, ranging from the individual level to the societal or collective whole, and how they both worked to create personal skills necessary for cultural safety skills of healthcare workers. This realization led me to consider the potential of integrating these models together into the revised HCA 111 course. By doing so, I believed I could significantly impact the wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety skills and knowledge of students in a holistic and informed manner that

blends both Western and Indigenous knowledge. In the upcoming pages, more information is provided on how the course revisions align with these models.

Project Overview

To inform this project, a comprehensive review of the literature was conducted. The review combined peer-reviewed articles on the wellness of post-secondary students in Canada with a particular focus on mental wellness in the Yukon. The literature also encompassed knowledge related to the risks and resilience of health care providers as well as insights into recommendations for educating students on cultural safety. Additionally, informal interviews with employed Yukon HCAs and guidance from Yukon First Nations Elders were sought to gather practical perspectives. The overall objective was to utilize this information to revise a course that would promote the resilience and wellness of Yukon University HCA program graduates. This would effectively align with the expectations of the Yukon healthcare system and enable culturally safe care for Indigenous health care recipients. It is my belief that the key to creating an effective, safe and sustainable workforce lies in educating health care providers about wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety.

Involvement of Elder Nina in the Project

During my years of teaching in the HCA Program with Yukon University, I have had the privilege of working with and learning from the Elders on campus. At times, I have asked to have an Elder be present in a class to offer thoughts or guidance on a specific subject, or to be present as a support for an emotionally or spiritually challenging class. What I witnessed during the classes at which an Elder was present was a change in the energy and attentiveness of students when the Elder was speaking, and even during their silence. Furthermore, I witnessed that some quiet and withdrawn students would use their voices in a new or different way.

Following these particular classes, I would hear students referring to learnings from the Elder and speaking about how these learnings had a deep impact to their worldview.

Early in the planning process, I connected to the Elder on Campus program at Yukon University to express my interest in connecting with an Elder for conversations about the project. I felt that in order to work towards positive change for wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety in HCA program at Yukon University, Elder support, guidance, knowledge, and connection would be essential. Elder Nina Bolton, of Carcross Tagish First Nation, graciously agreed to meet with me to discuss the purpose of the project and its associated goals, providing invaluable suggestions to guide the course revisions. Furthermore, Elder Nina expressed her willingness to actively participate in planning and teaching the revised course during the fall term of 2022, assuming the role of a First Nations Elder on campus. Her continuous feedback and insightful suggestions were indispensable throughout all stages of revising the HCA 111 course, and this project would not have been possible without her knowledge, wisdom, and willingness to take this journey with me.

Positionality of this Project

As a registered nurse, I have lived and worked as a settler on the traditional territory of the Kwanlin Dün First Nation (KDFN) and with the Ta'an Kwäch'än Council (TKC) in the Yukon since 2012. This unique position has shaped my perspective and understanding of health care and its impact on diverse communities. It is important for me to acknowledge my positionality as a settler and recognize the significance of addressing the specific needs of Indigenous communities in healthcare.

Background

Health Care Assistants in Canada

HCA's in Canada are unregulated front-line caregivers who provide personal care and assistance to patients in various healthcare settings. Despite the expanding job opportunities in the country, the exact number of HCA's working across Canada remains unknown (Canadian Institute for Health Information, 2022). HCA's are often overlooked in research; current statistics frequently group them with other allied health providers, making it challenging to obtain meaningful information about this credential and its implementation nationwide. Considering the significance of HCA's in the healthcare system, the scarcity of data and research about them highlights the need to address their unique challenges and promote their well-being.

Health Care Assistants in the Yukon

In my role as an HCA educator in the Yukon, I have developed an understanding of how HCA's are employed throughout the Yukon and in the community requests for HCA education. HCA's are employed throughout the Yukon, primarily in locations like long-term care, home care, and (in smaller numbers) acute care and outreach organizations. The primary employer is the Government of Yukon, but local First Nations health organizations have increased the number of employed HCA's. Most HCA's work in Yukon's capital, Whitehorse, but HCA's are found in most Yukon communities. Historically, it was challenging for HCA's working in the community to have permanent work because it was an issue for the primary employers (Yukon Government and local First Nations Health organizations) to translate the fluctuating needs of the public in smaller communities into permanent paid positions. This reality often resulted in HCA's from a given community working on call in their HCA capacity or, in some cases, the HCA would leave a smaller community. Recently, many smaller communities have been advocating for a greater number of permanent HCA positions and requesting educational

programming be made available in the communities to support the growing need for this critical level of care provider.

Health Care Assistant Program at Yukon University

The HCA program at Yukon University is an intensive program that consists of 14 courses over two terms, 270 hours of practicum time, and a total of 39 credit hours required for graduation. Each fall, the program admits 15 full-time students; typically, approximately half of the cohort comprises students who have immigrated to Canada, often from the Philippines. The program also reserves six seats for Yukon First Nations students, though only one to three of these seats are usually filled in a typical year. After graduation, HCA students become entry-level caregivers and are expected to work in understaffed, stressed, and resource-limited healthcare systems.

The current orientation of the HCA program includes cultural education about Yukon's First Nations peoples, experiential learning through the KAIROS Blanket Exercise, and a land-based workshop focused on trauma-informed care, all within the context of partnering effectively with First Nations community members. Additionally, students receive personal and community wellness education through one of the program's core courses, HCA 111. While these components provide foundational knowledge for students interacting with First Nations people across the Yukon, there are opportunities to deepen these understandings in teaching. Therefore, a learning opportunity has been identified to further develop students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes by integrating wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education through course revisions of HCA 111.

Health Care Assistant Role Challenges

HCAAs encounter various challenges that affect their well-being and the quality of care they provide. These challenges include workplace stress, heavy workloads, high turnover rates, low job satisfaction, and inadequate resources in health care settings (Armstrong et al., 2020; Estabrooks et al., 2015). Notably, most skilled labour in long-term care settings across Canada is performed by women, many of whom are racialized and, or, new to the country, according to a report by the Canadian Centre for Policy Alternatives (Armstrong et al., 2020, p. 7).

HCAAs often lack necessary preparedness for the increasing complexity of their roles in healthcare. Staffing levels and staff skill sets have not kept pace with the rising complexity and acuity of care provided in long-term care facilities (Estabrooks et al., 2015). Inadequate resources, capacity, structures, time, and support further hinder optimal care conditions in environments such as long-term care (Armstrong et al., 2020). The lack of requirements to which educational organizations must adhere when providing HCA education combined with the fact that HCAAs tend to have the lowest level of education among direct care providers, further exacerbates the risks faced by HCAAs and their clients (Zagrodney et al., 2022). Thus, significant challenges arise when unregulated front-line care providers are not prepared with the necessary education to care for vulnerable populations.

Risks to Wellness and Resilience of Health Care Assistants in the Yukon

HCAAs in the Yukon face challenges to wellness and resiliency that impact their ability to sustain lasting careers in healthcare. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, HCAAs in the Yukon provided care in systems that were often short staffed and overworked. The COVID-19 pandemic has further strained the wellness and resilience of care providers, leading to staffing shortages in community health centres and reduced available services (Government of Yukon, 2022a). Tracy-Anne McPhee, the Minister of Health for the Yukon, emphasized the reality and

urgency of health care provider burnout, stating, “Health care provider burnout is a real and pressing issue here at home and around the world” (Government of Yukon, 2022a, para. 2). Systemic level issues that relate to stress on healthcare systems must be addressed, but it is outside the scope of this project to make systemic level recommendations. As the scope of this project is to prepare individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills for their own practice the aim of the project is to recommend specific education about wellness and resiliency for Yukon University HCA students to mitigate the risk of caregiver burnout and to support success in their future roles.

Cultural Safety Education: Health Care Assistants in the Yukon

Cultural safety education is essential for HCAs to ensure they can provide appropriate care to Yukon’s Indigenous patients. Although specific statistics on Indigenous-specific racism and discrimination in the Yukon are not available, the Yukon Medical Council (YMC) acknowledges the existence of “Indigenous-specific racism in medicine and medical regulation” and commits to recognizing it as professional misconduct (Yukon Medical Council, 2021, p. 1). A comprehensive review of health and social programs and services conducted by the Government of Yukon in 2020 highlighted the experiences of Indigenous citizens who faced racism and stereotyping when accessing primary and acute care services (Government of Yukon, 2020, p. 25). To address this issue, the government developed 76 recommendations to improve health and social services for Yukoners. However, as of the 2022 progress update, several significant recommendations, including partnering with Indigenous and municipal governments, non-governmental organizations, and the public to ensure long-term planning of culturally safe health and social services, had not yet been implemented (Government of Yukon, 2022b, p. 12).

Ensuring culturally safe care for Indigenous recipients within the healthcare system is a clear and pressing concern and cultural safety education is crucial for health care providers in the Yukon.

Key Definitions in the Literature

Mental Health, Wellness and Resilience

The definitions for mental health and wellness utilized in this project are derived from the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Yukon First Nation Wellness Framework. According to the WHO, *mental health* is described as “a state of well-being in which an individual realizes their abilities, can cope with normal life stresses, can work productively, and is able to contribute to their community” (World Health Organization, 2018, para. 2). This definition underscores the holistic nature of mental health, encompassing various facets of an individual’s well-being.

Similarly, the Yukon First Nation Wellness Framework defines *wellness* as “a holistic balance of physical, spiritual, mental, and emotional well-being,” that aims to foster flourishing communities and individuals (Health and Social Development Commission, 2015, p. 2).

Addressing the mental health and wellness needs of students holds the potential to enhance the resilience of future health care professionals. *Resilience*, as described by Luthar et al. (2000), involves a “dynamic process encompassing positive adaptation within the context of significant adversity” (p. 543).

Compassion Fatigue and Burnout

The literature review conducted for this project underscores the significance of compassion fatigue and burnout in relation to the well-being and resilience of health care providers. *Compassion fatigue* is characterized as the strain on caregivers’ connections to empathy, compassion, and hope (TEND Academy [TEND], 2019). Left unmanaged, it can lead to caregivers leaving their positions due to burnout. *Burnout*, as outlined by Mathieu (2012), is

marked by emotional and physical exhaustion in demanding work environments, low job satisfaction, feelings of powerlessness, and being overwhelmed, often resulting in a desire to change jobs.

Cultural Safety

Cultural safety education within health care programs has the potential to address the needs of health care workers and Yukon Indigenous health care recipients. For this project, the definition of *cultural safety* aligns with the *In Plain Sight* report (2020):

A culturally safe environment can only be defined by the Indigenous person receiving care and does not profile or discriminate against the person but is experienced as respectful, safe and allows meaningful communication and service. It is a physically, socially, emotionally and spiritually safe environment, without challenge, ignorance or denial of an individual's identity (p. 11).

Land-Based Learning

Land-based learning is designed to address students' holistic well-being, encompassing their mental, emotional, spiritual, and physical needs. In this context, 'land-based learning' is precisely defined as follows:

A culturally defined program or service that takes place in an urban nature-based, rural, or remote location, which involves cultural teachings and intergenerational knowledge transfer, combined with any number of other activities or goals. Programs are informed by an Indigenous pedagogy wherein the land is the main source of knowledge and teaching (Redvers & Institute for Circumpolar Health Research, 2020, p. 90).

By incorporating such land-based learning experiences, HCA 111 not only equips students with valuable skills but also enriches their understanding of cultural safety and the interconnectedness of well-being with the land.

Community-Based Experiential Learning

Community-based experiential learning is an integral component of the revised HCA 111 curriculum, offering students the opportunity to actively engage in community events.

Community-based experiential learning enriches their understanding of social determinants of health, resource utilization, and community well-being. Learners reflect on in-class knowledge related to individual and community wellness, social determinants of health, and health equity before embarking on community placements. During these placements, students gain practical insights and contribute directly to community well-being.

Elder-led Learning

Elder-Led Learning encompasses the use of storytelling and traditional practices to enhance students' wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety. Leveraging the knowledge and support of Elders plays a crucial role in improving students' overall well-being. As articulated in The First Nations Mental Wellness Continuum Framework, Elders hold significant leadership roles within their communities, offering guidance, sharing wisdom, and imparting traditional knowledge and languages (Health and Social Development Commission, 2015). Incorporating Elders into education ensures an equitable blend of Western and Indigenous knowledge, shaping culturally safe approaches to care and fostering meaningful connections with students.

Literature Review

A comprehensive review of existing literature was conducted to inform the project. The literature review played a pivotal role in examining various aspects related to wellness and

resiliency, focusing on post-secondary students and health care workers, and delving into the importance of wellness and resiliency education, as well as cultural safety education within the healthcare field. Key topics addressed in the literature review included caregiver burnout, Indigenous-specific racism, and discrimination prevalent in the Yukon healthcare system.

The Search

A literature review explored evidence-based educational strategies for fostering cultural safety among nurses and nursing students. The search was conducted via the University of Northern British Columbia's Library and included the databases: Academic Search Complete, CINAHL Complete, MEDLINE, and ERIC. These databases were selected for their relevance to health, health systems, and education. Literature selected consisted primarily of Canadian peer-reviewed studies published in English from the year 2018 to 2023. Grey literature was used for accessing information related to health care workforces, cultural safety, resiliency and wellness of health care workers. Grey literature included statistics, information from First Nations health and wellness organizations, and Yukon- and Canada-specific reports relating to HCAs. The information collected from this review will be discussed in greater detail below.

Student Wellness and Resiliency Education

Yukon post-secondary students, particularly Indigenous individuals, require improved mental wellness support due to significant barriers to accessing relevant and timely mental health services in Northern Canada (Xiong et al., 2020). Although specific data on the mental health status of students at Yukon University is currently limited, findings from the College Health Assessment of Canadian Post-secondary Students (2020) reveal concerning trends. In the previous year, over 60% of students experienced above-average or tremendous levels of stress, with more than half struggling with depression that impaired their functioning, and 16%

seriously contemplating suicide (Mental Health Commission of Canada, 2020b). These statistics underscore the urgent need for tailored wellness education for Yukon Indigenous populations.

The pandemic has exacerbated these challenges, as evidenced by data collected during this period. Indigenous individuals experienced a significant decline in mental well-being, with 60% of respondents reporting deteriorating mental health. This included symptoms consistent with generalized anxiety disorder and heightened stress levels, which were notably higher than non-Indigenous individuals (Arriagada et al., 2020, para. 7). This highlights the urgency of addressing mental health disparities in Indigenous communities through targeted wellness education.

Health Care Worker Wellness and Resiliency Education

Enhancing student wellness through resiliency education is crucial not only for students but also for health care workers. The emotional demands of the healthcare profession, coupled with the increasing complexity of healthcare, have led to high levels of compassion fatigue among nurses (Maillet & Read, 2021). The pandemic exacerbated these challenges, leading to high stress levels among registered nurses (RNs) and projections of an exodus from the profession (Registered Nurses' Association of Ontario, 2021; BCNU, 2021). While data specific to HCAs is limited, the similarities in the caring roles of HCAs and RNs suggest that they face comparable mental health challenges.

Literature demonstrates that resilient caregivers are more likely to remain in the workforce, with a resilience-based approach identified as beneficial in reducing burnout and turnover rates among nurses (Ang et al., 2018; Mathieu, 2012). Given the lack of clear recommendations for evidence-based resilience education for health care students and insufficient evidence regarding strategies to address resilience and mental health in healthcare

workers (Buselli et al., 2021), it is imperative for educational health programs to integrate new strategies to support the well-being of future caregivers.

Trauma and Cultural Safety Education

In seeking to understand cultural safety education, it is crucial to recognize the severe trauma inflicted on the health and well-being of Canada's Indigenous peoples because of colonization. This trauma results from systemic discrimination, racism, the Indian Act and Indian Reservations, the direct and intergenerational traumas of the Residential school system, the destruction of cultural traditions and practices by the legal system, the removal of children from their birth families by Canada's child protection agencies, and the social exclusion of Indigenous people (Schill & Caxaj, 2019). These factors have contributed to increased health disparities among Indigenous populations in Canada, including reduced access to family physicians, higher burdens of chronic and infectious diseases, inequitable education access, and inadequate funding for sanitation, housing, safe water, and health services on reserves (Schill & Caxaj, 2019).

To address the intergenerational and historical traumas experienced by Indigenous people, caregiving professions must adopt meaningful and safe approaches that promote health and healing. It is imperative that current systems address microaggressions, discrimination, racism, and harassment (O'Neill et al., 2018). Unfortunately, the healthcare system, which is intended to provide assistance, perpetuates discrimination against and harm to Indigenous individuals.

Many health care students undergo courses designed to sensitize them to formal ritual and practice rather than to the emotional, social, economic and political context in which people exist. In health care, it is important for providers to take the cultural needs of patients into consideration, not just have knowledge of ritual and practice of different cultures. Leninger

(1991) highlights that culture is “Learned, shared and transmitted values, beliefs, norms, and lifeways of a particular group that guides their thinking, decisions, and actions in patterned ways” (p.47). Likewise, Ramsden (2002) elaborated further that the term “cultural safety” was coined by a Māori nursing student in the late 1980’s. She made a plea at a meeting of health educators by saying, “you talk of ethical safety, legal safety and physical safety...what about cultural safety?” Simply put, cultural safety is defined by those who receive the service (Ramsden, 2002). Cultural safety education is of critical importance in health care education because it provides students with experience in allowing patients to inform care givers of what they require rather than having the care givers assume that they have the answers. Embedded in cultural safety, we include humility. Cultural safety education will often remind students to remain humble.

Cultural safety education for health care professionals represents a meaningful approach to creating a safe and inclusive healthcare system for Canada’s Indigenous populations. Cultural safety aims to establish an environment in which individuals from diverse cultures feel safe, respected, and supported. It acknowledges the impact of power imbalances, historical trauma, and systemic inequalities on marginalized or minority groups. Cultural safety involves actively addressing and challenging these imbalances, fostering open dialogue, and promoting inclusivity and equity. Moreover, cultural safety emphasizes the importance of individuals and institutions reflecting on their own practices and power dynamics to ensure acknowledgment, honouring, and protection of cultural differences. Ultimately, cultural safety entails delivering care that is deemed safe based on the perspectives and experiences of the service recipient rather than solely on the provider’s viewpoint (Gerlach et al., 2017).

In addition to addressing the needs of Indigenous peoples and creating safe healthcare systems, cultural safety education has the potential to align with the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada's Calls to Action (numbers 22 to 24) and the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples Act (Government of Canada, 2021). Lastly, cultural safety practices can serve to disrupt the discriminatory practices and policies within the healthcare system (Gerlach et al., 2017).

Through this extensive examination of existing literature, the review served to guide the incorporation of essential elements into the course revision framework, ensuring its relevance and effectiveness in addressing the identified concerns. The next steps involved developing an educational strategy that integrates wellness and resiliency education for HCA students at Yukon University, with a specific focus on cultural safety education to address the unique needs of Indigenous populations in the Yukon.

Theoretical Frameworks and Knowledge Systems

Two theoretical models were identified during the literature review: the socio-ecological model and First Nations perspective on health and wellness. These models were selected to address the promotion of a culturally safe workforce and to support the reduction of caregiver burnout. In addition to theoretical models, the Indigenous knowledge systems of Two-Eyed seeing and the cultural principles of learning (9 Rs) were incorporated into the framework of the course redesign to deepen the connection of learnings on wellness, resilience, and cultural safety for the HCA students.

Socio-ecological Model

The socio-ecological model, utilized by the Canadian Standards Association (CSA Group, 2020) to develop national wellness standards for post-secondary students, was chosen

due to its holistic approach to promoting positive mental health and well-being among post-secondary students. This evidence-based model aligned with the project's goal of revising the HCA course to incorporate wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education for students (see Figure 1 for the socio-ecological model).

The socio-ecological model comprises individual, interpersonal, institutional, community, and society and it is these components that conceptualize wellness and resiliency (Ma et al., 2017). This model was instrumental in guiding course revisions by providing a comprehensive framework for wellness and resiliency education and identifying opportunities for cultural safety education. In the model, overlapping circles that represent each level depict the interdependence and influence of one level on the next (CSA Group, 2020).

Individual Level

The individual level, which is at the centre of the socio-ecological model, encompasses an individual's knowledge, skills, behaviours, attitudes, and bio-psychosocial characteristics (CSA Group, 2020; Zhu et al., 2020). Self-awareness plays a crucial role in wellness and resiliency because it enables individuals to identify their knowledge and wellness needs (Krug & Dahlberg, 2006).

Interpersonal Level

The interpersonal level of the socio-ecological model encapsulates the individual and represents the relationships and interactions of the individual with peers, friends, family, and other social networks (CSA Group, 2020). Within the interpersonal layer, an individual develops relationships and connections with others and this shapes wellness and resiliency by impacting their choices, behaviours, experiences, and sense of safety when seeking help or resources (Krug & Dahlberg, 2006).

Institutional Level

The institutional level, includes settings in which individuals are actively engaged, such as schools, workplaces, and the built environment (CSA Group, 2020; Zhu et al., 2020). These settings impact wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety based on the safety of the environment, the availability of resources, and systemic structures within institutions (Zhu et al., 2020).

Community Level

The community level, encompasses cultural values, norms, identity groups, belief systems, lifestyles, and bodies of knowledge (CSA Group, 2020). This level aims to impact an individual's sense of safety and belonging within their cohort and the broader community.

Societal Level

The societal level, the final layer of the socio-ecological model, encompasses public policies and laws that impact individuals (CSA Group, 2020). This level is central in educating individuals about the structural factors that affect wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety. Making changes at the societal level usually demands the greatest effort to effect change (Krug & Dahlberg, 2006).

Figure 1

Socio-ecological model

(CSA Group, 2020, p. 19)

First Nations Perspective on Health and Wellness Model

To ensure cultural safety and inclusivity, the project also embraced the First Nations perspective on health and wellness. The First Nations perspective on health and wellness model (Figure 2), developed by British Columbia's First Nations Health Authority (FNHA, 2017), provides a comprehensive framework for understanding wellness from an Indigenous perspective. This model provides a holistic vision of wellness by considering internal and external factors that impact well-being and incorporates traditional Indigenous knowledge (First Nations Health Authority, 2014, p. 49). Before adapting the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model for use in the southern Yukon region, I consulted with two local Elders to ensure its appropriateness. Both Elders expressed support for use of the model in the Yukon, and for the pairing with the socio-ecological model. Elder Nina, who played a pivotal role in this project, emphasized that the First Nations Holistic Wellness model supports care providers in

“being mindful that you are working with a human being” and reminds them “not to lose the humanness in this work” (S. Soo, personal communication, May 16, 2023).

This model consists of interconnected circles that represent several aspects of wellness. Starting with the Centre Circle, which represents individual responsibility, the model expands outward to explore values, relationships, and determinants of well-being. The Outer Circle symbolizes togetherness, respect, and relationships within a community (FNHA, 2014). It is essential to note that the circles in the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model are not hierarchical levels but are, rather, interconnected components that contribute to holistic wellness (FNHA, 2014)

Figure 2

The First Nations perspective on health and wellness model

(FNHA, 2017, p. 2)

Indigenous Knowledge System Application

The project further supported creating holistic knowledge and skills to promote the wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety of HCA students by integrating Two-Eyed Seeing and cultural principles of learning, hereafter referred to as the 9 Rs.

Two-Eyed Seeing

Two-Eyed Seeing is a concept that encourages the integration of Indigenous and Western ways of knowing and recognizes the value of understanding multiple perspectives to gain a more comprehensive worldview. By having Elder Nina's involvement, this project embraced the principles of Two-Eyed Seeing, acknowledging the importance of both Indigenous and Western knowledge systems in promoting holistic wellness and cultural safety.

Cultural Principles for Establishing Meaningful, Safe and Ethical Relationships (9 Rs)

The 9 Rs (listed below) are comprised of nine cultural principles that provided a scaffold for establishing meaningful cultural and ethical relationships among different knowledge holders, systems, and communities for the design and delivery of this project. The principles were identified and articulated by Dr. Tina Fraser, a Māori scholar from Aotearoa (New Zealand) teaching at the University of Northern British Columbia (Soo, September 22, 2023). Dr. Fraser possesses expertise related to indigenous knowledge related to health, education, and wellness along with advanced knowledge of cultural safety principles. As a supervisor of this project, she identified the principles as a core framework for the work completed in the course revisions of HCA 111. The cultural principles include respect, relationships, responsibilities, reciprocity, relevance, reverence, reclamation, reconciliation, and reflexivity.

Respect.

Respect works in many forms from the individual to the collective and centres around the belief that we as people must begin with our inner space of self. This means that we begin exploring our own identity of who we are, where we came from, where we are today and what legacy we want to leave for our future generations. Respecting all forms of life is a reminder that we come from different worldviews. Once we have a good grasp on self-identity, we will have a better sense of exploring the outer space and understanding “all our relations.”

Relationships.

Relationships between people, place and land are critical to our existence. As people, we are connected to each other, and our kinship ties are linked genealogically and geographically. Our language allows us to connect to our ancestors, the knowledge holders of songs, stories, prayers, incantations, dance, spirituality, and the dream world. We use all our senses through looking, listening, touching, smelling and tasting. Our traditional stories remind us of the past, present, and future, and the stories are transmitted intergenerationally so we can carry on the good deeds and our responsibilities to our ancestors.

Responsibilities.

Responsibilities are a collective practice. Community members are often guided by the Elders, knowledge holders or through leadership. Many cultural responsibilities stem from peripheral learning. As children grow and develop, Elders are constantly watching for unique skills amongst children and youth and often, they will mentally, emotionally, physically, spiritually, and socially prepare them for the future. In many cases and through observation, children will mimic such skills as the language where listening and looking are required. Teenagers may be skilled at hunting, fishing, gathering and foraging in order to prepare for the winter months or the children might learn about the different plants, purpose (internal or external

use), and traditionally, the prayers, songs, and incantations for each of those plants. As the children and youth grow with knowledge, they become responsible for the gathering and dissemination of the knowledge(s) passed down. Sharing of what they have learned is a way of “gifting back.”

Reciprocity.

Traditionally, gifting goes beyond “just giving.” It allows individuals to appreciate people, place, and land and not just take things for granted. We are often thankful when we communicate with each other because of new knowledge that is shared or exchanged amongst each other. A good example of this form of reciprocity are, researchers entering communities through communicating, engaging, listening, dialoguing, and/or interviewing someone or something. We are often seeking to find an answer for to fulfill our curiosity. This is a natural process for human beings however, as researchers or visitors, one must pay attention to the gathering of knowledge and most of all, who benefits and why? A simple conversation with any community member often means you will be walking away with something of interest.

Reciprocity must come from the heart and not for the simple fact of just giving, but rather, “I really appreciated the Elder who took his/her valuable time to share things that might be helpful for me to give back to the community.” Most often, the community will not ask for things but if there is one great contribution people could do for the community, it would be to explore something relevant for the people, by the people, and with the people.

Relevance.

For protocols to be successful when entering communities, researchers and visitors must have some understanding of the historical events that took place in that location; loss of identity, loss of language, loss of connection to place and space, traditional and cultural practices, cultural

laws and structures. As researchers and visitors, we should be culturally aware of the “do and do not” and not assume that all communities have the same protocols or that the protocols are used for the same events or practices. There are unique traits amongst the individual, family, community, nations, locally, provincially, nationally, and internationally.

Reverence.

Indigenous people will share stories that personify lessons to be learned and taught. Their creation stories are connected to the animal world; mother earth and everything that encompasses nature, the environment, and the eco-systems that allow Indigenous people to survive rather than destroy all things that is animate and imbued with spirit. As cultural beings, we require water to stay afloat, to feel the energy and synergy provided by the creator. It is well noted by many Elders that, “we are the land and the land is us or, we are the river and the river is us.” Each community are abundantly blessed with proverbial sayings that have been a part of their history since time immemorial.

Reclamation.

As Indigenous people strive to reclaim their ways of knowing and being, there is a strong movement to reclaiming the essence of cultural practices, language revitalization, traditions, stories, songs, incantations, customs and protocols, treaties/land claims, preservation, and sustainability. Reclamation begins with the individual in search of their identity and including family, community, and nation. To reclaim traditional ways of knowing and being, it takes the collective.

Reconciliation.

According to the Truth and Reconciliation (2015), reconciliation is a process of healing of relationships that require public truth sharing, apology, and commemoration which

acknowledge and redress past harms (p. 4). It also requires constructive action on addressing the ongoing legacies of colonialism that have had destructive impact on Indigenous peoples' education, cultures and languages, health, child welfare, the administration of justice, and economic opportunities and prosperity (p.4). What will it take to acknowledge the past injustices in contemporary times? We all share responsibilities therefore, reconciling accountability, trust, collectivity, leadership, and respectful relationships are all necessary.

Reflexivity.

We all have different beliefs and practices, but what is important to note is how we view our journey, the influences that helps people to become enlightened, and most importantly, what we do with the knowledge. Reflexivity allows us the ability and awareness of how our beliefs, values, experiences, and practices become positive. Applying the nine cultural principles for meaningful relationships within the project helped me to develop a strong connection with Elder Nina and allowed me to draw on and apply the 9R's to all aspects of this project. These principles guided me to a place of acknowledgement, recognition and appreciation and facilitated further understanding of resiliency, wellness, and cultural safety as it applies to HCA education. Understanding the foundational pieces; the theoretical models, knowledge and approaches which support this project allowed me to move into the discovering, dreaming, designing, and delivering segment of the project.

Discovering, Dreaming, Designing, and Delivering

This project employed an appreciative inquiry approach to enhance wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education in the HCA program at Yukon University. Appreciative inquiry (AI) was chosen as the approach due to its inclusive, strength-based methodology, which focuses on identifying and building upon positive aspects and pieces to implement improvements

(Shuayb et al., 2009). AI was also selected for this project because it is used to build resilience and grit within systems and organizations that are experiencing widespread challenges. As identified in the background, HCA students are entering health care at a time when students, staff, and healthcare systems are vulnerable and in crisis.

AI is widely recognized for its effectiveness in implementing educational planning initiatives and harnessing the energy to affect change in organizations or systems (Shuayb et al., 2009). This approach emphasizes collaboration and the involvement of participants, ensuring their voices and experiences are incorporated into this project. The AI approach is structured around four phases: discovering, dreaming, designing, and delivering and these phases will be explored below (Shuayb et al., 2009).

Discovering (Exploring)

In the AI process, *discovering* allows for identification and appreciation of “the best of what is” (Shuayb et al., 2009). Typically, the discovery phase of inquiry consists of asking open-ended questions of interview subjects to learn about an organization’s strengths and weaknesses. This project utilized a literature review in the discovery phase to gain a deeper understanding of wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education. The literature review served as a foundational step in ‘discovering’ in order to gain an understanding of existing knowledge, theories, and practice (Shuayb et al., 2009), and to understand the strengths and weaknesses of the healthcare system and health care education. Discovering facilitated the identification of gaps, challenges, and successful interventions, and thus provided a solid basis for the subsequent AI phases. Discovering highlighted pressing concerns such as caregiver burnout, Indigenous-specific racism, and discrimination within the Yukon healthcare system. It also explored the wellness and resilience education needs of Yukon University HCA students, the impact of the COVID-19

pandemic on Canadians' mental wellness, and the challenges to, and urgent need for wellness support among Yukon post-secondary students, particularly the Indigenous population.

Discovering underscored the need for wellness education, resilience education, and cultural safety education within the HCA program to address the unique needs of future health care professionals and ensure safe and culturally sensitive care. Discovering further highlighted the need for improved mental wellness support among Yukon post-secondary students; this is especially true for Indigenous students, who face greater risks to their mental wellness.

As the discovering phase laid a comprehensive foundation by revealing critical insights and gaps, the subsequent dreaming phase leveraged this knowledge to envision innovative approaches and solutions for advancing wellness, resilience, and cultural safety education for Yukon University HCA students.

Dreaming (Envisioning)

The dreaming phase of the AI methodology involves envisioning and planning "what might be" (Shuayb et al., 2009, p. 4). In this phase, creativity is encouraged to better explore possibilities and potential improvements. During the dreaming phase, I sought to use the information and perspectives found in the discovering phase to create ideas for how to promote wellness, resilience, and cultural safety education for Yukon University HCA students.

As part of the HCA 111 course revision, the information gathered from a 14-day visit to northern Scandinavian colleges and universities and from informal conversations with international educators, employed HCAs, and local Elders played a significant role in this phase. The conversations with employed HCAs and local Elders moved the information gleaned from the discovering stage and the practical learnings with international educators, into a Yukon-specific context to help support the revision of the HCA 111 course. The discovering stage; the

literature review, theoretical models and informal conversations with students, educators, HCA's and local Elders also facilitated rich interwoven dialogue, which for the purpose of the dreaming phase, is termed interwoven perspectives.

Interwoven Perspective One: Travelling Knowledge—Looking, Listening, and Learning

My course revision project evolved to include a 14-day expedition to visit various northern Scandinavian colleges and universities. During the trip I had the privilege of immersing myself in a wealth of experiences and insights which allowed me to view the practical realities of how other remote northern educators deliver programs related to wellness, resilience, and cultural safety in health care education. Through the journey, I looked at how these institutions worked to respond to the wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety needs within health care through programming and regulated competencies. I listened to the stories of educators who have worked to create change within curriculum and programs and heard their recommendations for program revisions. By attending the various colleges and universities, I was able to identify how these institutions were including cultural safety education, land-based teaching and learning, and the teachings of traditional knowledge holders into educational programs. The active engagement of looking, listening, and learning on this trip played a pivotal role in facilitating the dreaming (envisioning) process (refer to Appendix A for the North2North: Northern European Network Trip report).

Looking: Insights into Indigenous Health Education

Among the universities visited, UiT Arctic University of Norway in Alta, Norway, stood out as the northernmost institution on the tour. Their nursing program strived to establish nursing competencies within the national standards framework surrounding cultural safety. New guidelines incorporated outcomes linked to knowledge and skills, and to attitudes related to

cultural safety. For example, students were required to identify and recognize the effects of collective trauma and provide cultural safety in their practice. Specifically, the new guideline on cultural safety in nursing education encompassed having the students develop an understanding how colonization processes affect human beings over time, recognizing the need to decolonize processes, and engaging in conversations about Indigenous health topics. The university's approach exemplified the potential for incorporating cultural safety in health care education and practice.

Listening: Embracing Indigenous Knowledge on Nature, Wellness, and Caring

The Luleå University of Technology in Luleå, Sweden, offered profound insights into wellness-focused programming. The nursing curriculum encompassed research topics related to the health benefits derived from connecting with nature for overall well-being, especially in the context of an Arctic environment. The university's emphasis on understanding health promotion throughout the lifespan and viewing nature as a health resource underscored its commitment to Indigenous care practices. During my interactions with faculty at the university, I inquired about the potential integration of land-based teachings into health education. The instructors emphasized the importance of creating an environment in which group members felt no pressure to interact but could share their experiences freely and validate each other positively, thereby fostering valuable interactions and learning. Inspired by these findings, I contemplated how to incorporate nature-based opportunities in my own course to prioritize students' wellness and resilience through self-care, growth, and autonomy. I concluded I would include group land-based learning within the revisions to HCA 111 and that I would plan to integrate this type of programming with local traditional knowledge holders.

Learning: Cultural Safety in Health Education

Lapland University in Rovaniemi, Finland, prioritized cultural safety for Indigenous populations in their nursing curriculum by integrating traditional storytelling, land-based education, and the inclusion of Elders as cultural resources for teachers. These Elders supported the development and dissemination of cultural and traditional knowledge within courses. The Sámi University of Applied Sciences in Kautokeino, Norway, emphasized the Northern Sámi language and made it the language of instruction, with Elders actively involved in knowledge transmission. Nord University in Bodø, Norway, collaborated with UiT in Tromsø to conduct culturally sensitive research on care for Sámi Indigenous people and aimed to further integrate Sámi culture and language into their nursing education. These experiences highlight these institutions' efforts to enhance the well-being of health care students, incorporate Indigenous knowledge, promote cultural safety, and integrate traditional culture and knowledge into health care education.

Interwoven Perspective Two: Conversations with Health Care Assistant Employees

To gain deeper insight into the requirements for student wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education, I conducted informal conversations with six HCAs employed in the Yukon. The purpose was to identify strengths within the healthcare system and opportunities for improvement when creating safer practices. I posed the question, “What helps you stay in this job?” Their responses included 1) fostering positive relationships with colleagues, 2) feeling valued and achieving work-life balance by managing their shifts, 3) receiving respect from management, 4) participating in debriefing sessions following critical events, and 5) having the ability to voice concerns and address workplace challenges.

Regarding the incorporation of wellness and resiliency education for HCA students, the HCAs recommended educating students about the importance of not taking on excessive

responsibilities too quickly in their initial health care roles, because this often leads to burnout. HCAs who had more than 10 years' experience (two out of the six) emphasized that they understood their own limits in terms of the number of shifts they could sustain and the signs that indicated excessive workload. These signs included feelings of exhaustion, diminished energy for personal life and activities outside of work, preoccupation with work even when not on duty, and reduced tolerance for life's usual challenges. Consequently, these informal conversations with employed HCAs served to validate the need to incorporate wellness and resiliency education into my HCA 111 course.

Interwoven Perspective Three: Conversations and Insight from a Yukon First Nations Elder

To gain insight into and perspective about the focus on cultural safety education in the revised HCA 111 course, I considered the involvement of a First Nations Elder to be a crucial component of the process. After establishing the initial plans, which I created from the discovery phase, I had the privilege of engaging a First Nations Elder associated with Yukon University to develop practical and culturally informed programming. Elder Nina Bolton graciously agreed to meet with me to discuss the purpose of the project and its associated goals; she provided invaluable suggestions to guide the course revisions. Furthermore, Elder Nina expressed her willingness to actively participate in planning and teaching the revised course during the fall term of 2022 and assumed the role of a First Nations Elder on campus. Involving Elder Nina in the process enabled the integration of Western and Indigenous knowledges on equal footings, employing a Two-Eyed Seeing approach that brings together the best of Western and traditional perspectives.

Interwoven Perspective Four: Using Theoretical Models to Guide Course Revisions

The socio-ecological model provided a framework for educating students about how to become safe caregivers who deliver competent and culturally sensitive care. The model emphasizes wellness, resilience, and cultural safety education. The socio-ecological model and the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model were employed together to reframe and focus the HCA 111 course on the holistic well-being of both students and health care recipients.

The circles within the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model align with the five levels of the socio-ecological model and enabled an integrated approach that combines Indigenous and Western perspectives in the course revisions. Using this Indigenous perspective, Elder Nina provided practical recommendations for teaching within each circle of the model. As an Elder and wellness practitioner experienced in working with vulnerable populations, she offered invaluable insights and guidance for the project including grounding activities during land-based learning activities, reflective self-awareness activities, community experiential activity locations, and storytelling to integrate cultural safety education in the classroom. Her overarching recommendation emphasized creating opportunities for students to be present in their own lives and to fully engage with their patients. According to Elder Nina, “our clients know when we’re with them and when we’re not. Patients pick up on whether we are addressing their holistic needs. You have the ability to make or break another person. It is important for you to know how to respond to them and to treat them” (S. Soo, personal communication, May 16, 2023).

The utilization of the Two-Eyed Seeing approach, which combines the socio-ecological model and the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model, directly aligned with project objectives. This approach encourages the use of multiple perspectives to enhance

outcomes (Michie et al., 2018, p. 1207). The incorporation of the 9 Rs further reinforced this approach, ensuring respect for Indigenous engagement and perspectives, relevance to students' realities, reciprocity, and student empowerment. By incorporating Two-Eyed Seeing and the 9 Rs, the course achieved holistic outcomes. This approach acknowledges Indigenous wisdom, integrates Western frameworks, and fosters culturally responsive learning.

Interwoven Perspective Five: Integrating Flexible and Responsive Content Delivery

Integrating flexible content delivery into the course revisions effectively addresses the unique needs and challenges faced by HCA students enrolled in the intensive HCA program at Yukon University. This pedagogical approach recognizes the significance of adaptability and student-centred learning, enabling personalized educational experiences and the allocation of class time specifically dedicated to project work. This interwoven perspective developed as a result of conversations with students during the revised course delivery and it was not a part of the original project design. During early conversations with students, they reported their feeling of stress and overwhelm with the quantity of the program assignments. In response to students' reports, I chose to create flexibility in the course schedule to grant course time to students to work on course assignments.

Designing: Course Revisions for HCA 111 - Analyzing and Synthesizing Perspectives

The designing process for revising the HCA 111 course, guided by AI methodology, involves synthesizing information from the discovering and interwoven perspectives from the dreaming phase. In alignment with AI principles, the course revisions for HCA 111 aim to create a nurturing learning environment for HCA students. Integrating the socio-ecological and First Nations health models, Elder Nina's wisdom, the principles of the 9 Rs, informal conversations and literature insights shaped these revisions. By applying Two-Eyed Seeing, the course

incorporates self-awareness, Elder-led, land-based, community experiential, and cultural safety learning. This holistic approach equips students with diverse skills for health care success. The designing stage is rebuilding and revising to create a stronger foundation using a pillared approach. In this project, a pillar is the fundamental element that provides support and stability for course revisions and the revamped course (Shuayb et al., 2009).

Pillar One: Self-awareness Learning

The core of HCA 111 course revisions lies in self-awareness learning, which functions as the foundational pillar for wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety. The First Nations perspective on health and wellness model places individuals at the centre and emphasizes their responsibility for nurturing their mental, emotional, physical, and spiritual well-being (FNHA, 2014). Self-awareness learning corresponds to the Centre (core of wellness) and Second Circles (aspects of wellness) of the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model. Similarly, the socio-ecological model's focus in the individual level emphasizes knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviours. Acknowledging biases and limitations for culturally safe care is a crucial for health care providers (Younas, 2020).

Elder Nina highlights the profound impact of self-awareness on students' wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety learning. With her endorsement, the wellness wheel provided by the First Nations Health Authority (FNHA) serves as a valuable tool to cultivate self-awareness and wellness self-assessment. This tool enables students to identify areas that need attention or support while considering physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual dimensions (FNHA, 2014). Mindfulness and self-reflection exercises, suggested by Elder Nina, connect students with the land and cultivate bodily presence, which are both grounding practices that heighten awareness of the body-mind-spirit interconnection. Regular utilization of the wellness wheel is encouraged

to prompt monthly self-checks and at-home assessments to prevent neglect of essential aspects of life. As Elder Nina affirms, “health care work’s demands can lead to neglect of significant aspects. Assessing the wellness wheel at home helps us remember what truly matters” (S. Soo, personal communication, May 16, 2022).

Integration of self-awareness and reflection into education enhances students’ understanding of their own and others’ needs. This equips them to be care providers who prioritize their well-being while fostering empathy and compassion for patients. Educators who incorporate self-awareness learning contribute to a health care culture of respect and understanding by fostering skillful and self-aware caregivers who ultimately enhance patient outcomes.

Pillar Two: Elder-led Learning

The integration of Elder-led learning into the curriculum aligns harmoniously with the interpersonal level of the socio-ecological model and the Third Circle (values of wellness) of the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model. The socio-ecological model underscores the significance of social networks, family, and friends to an individual’s health, while the Third Circle of the First Nations model emphasizes the essential elements of respect, responsibility, relationships, and wisdom for overall well-being (FNHA, 2014).

Incorporating Elder-led learning into the curriculum provides students with opportunities to cultivate bonds and connections, acknowledging the pivotal role of social ties that enhance resilience, as demonstrated by recent research by Holt-Lunstad (2021). Elder-led learning, with practices like storytelling, holds promise for enhancing students’ well-being, resilience, and cultural safety and integrating Elder-led learning bridges Western and Indigenous knowledge

systems to nurture culturally sensitive care approaches (S. Soo, personal communication, May 23, 2023).

Pillar Three: Land-Based Learning

Land-based learning effectively aligns with both the institutional level of the socio-ecological model and the Fourth Circle (context for wellness) of the First Nations perspective on health and wellness. The integration of land-based learning into HCA 111 is driven by the objective to cultivate wellness, resilience, and cultural safety education, with a central emphasis on fostering inclusive and supportive learning environments.

The multidimensional land-based learning approach equips students with lifelong tools, fostering resilience, self-awareness, and meaningful connections. This approach integrates self-awareness and Elder-led learning while harmonizing the principles of the socio-ecological and First Nations models. In my capacity as a Western-trained health care provider and instructor, I conscientiously aligned each land-based experience with a corresponding class learning outcome. Collaborating with Elder Nina, we enriched my land-based ideas with cultural and traditional learning activities. These encompassed mindfulness exercises, sharing circles, Elder-led narratives, and outdoor contemplation, all firmly grounded in Indigenous and Western research that recognizes the positive impact of nature-based learning on holistic well-being (CSA Group, 2020; deJong et al., 2021; Redvers & Institute for Circumpolar Health Research, 2020).

Pillar Four: Community Experiential Learning

The revised HCA 111 course prioritizes experiential learning by focusing on community programs, resources, and health determinants. This empowers students to understand the connections between wellness, resilience, and cultural safety in local contexts. Embracing the Fifth Circle (determinants of wellness) of the First Nations perspective on health and wellness

model acknowledges the influence of social, economic, cultural, and environmental factors on well-being (FNHA, 2017, p. 2). When exploring the community level of the socio-ecological model, the curriculum prompts students to engage with local initiatives to enhance their understanding of how community contributes to well-being, resilience, and cultural safety.

Inspired by the post-secondary community training recommendations from the Canadian Standards Association (2020) guidelines for post-secondary students' mental health and well-being, this approach allows students to experience community resources that influence, and are influenced by, social determinants of health in the communities where students live, learn, work and play. Experiential learning in the community equips students with insights about resources and factors that shape holistic well-being. This immersion enables understanding of cultural values, norms, and identity dynamics that affect wellness. Putting into practice Elder Nina's suggestions, such as involvement in local food banks, clinics, culture camps, and wellness initiatives, can deepen students' connections to the community.

Pillar Five: Cultural Safety Education

The HCA 111 course revisions demonstrate a holistic approach to cultivating cultural safety awareness among health care students. The primary aim of cultural safety is to establish an equitable and secure environment for all cultural groups by addressing power dynamics (Stevenson & Tobias, 2023, p. 3). These revisions harmonize aspects from the socio-ecological model's society level, the Fifth (determinants of wellness) and Outer Circles (our community) of the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model, the 9 Rs, and the *In Plain Sight* report recommendations (2020), fostering a comprehensive and informed understanding of culturally safe care.

The socio-ecological model, particularly its society level, unveils the impact of policies and legal frameworks on health that are critical to understanding cultural safety complexities, including decolonization and systemic discrimination. Incorporating the Fifth and Outer Circle of the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model enriches the revisions; these circles emphasize social, economic, cultural, and environmental factors in health (FNHA, 2017, p. 2). Aligned with Recommendation 21 of the *In Plain Sight* report, the cultural safety education revisions to HCA 111 ensure students receive training on indigenous-specific racism, colonialism, trauma-informed practice, and the importance of meeting the minimum standards outlined in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which are provided in course readings and class conversations (Turpel-Lafond, 2020, p. 200).

Pillar Six: Flexible and Responsive Content Delivery

Flexible and responsive content delivery is listed in this project as an interwoven perspective and as a design pillar because of its emergence in student feedback and its importance in the delivery of the course. The incorporation of flexible content delivery addresses the unique needs of HCA students in the intensive program at Yukon University. This approach prioritizes adaptability, student-centred learning, and dedicated project time. It fosters collaboration, critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity.

To enhance student engagement and tailor the course to their preferences, multiple opportunities for input have been integrated into the curriculum. This enables students to express their preferences regarding what they would like to see more or less of within the course. The primary objective of these measures is to ensure that the course remains responsive to the evolving needs and interests of the students, thereby making the learning experience more meaningful. The flexible content delivery approach not only enriches the learning experience by

accommodating student preferences but also supports their holistic well-being. It represents a holistic and adaptive strategy that aligns with the unique requirements of HCA students in the intensive program at Yukon University, promoting their academic success and overall development. As the comprehensive foundation of the six pillars took shape during the designing phase, the subsequent delivering stage, marked by meticulous planning and collaboration, brought these course revisions to life.

Delivering (Executing)

The delivering stage of the AI methodology entailed the execution of the revised HCA 111 course. Within this phase, the approach involves translating the formulated plans into action. This stage was characterized by careful planning and collaboration with Elder Nina, whose contributions of traditional knowledge, grounding activities, and teachings about connection between the self, others, and the land were pivotal to enhancing student understanding, well-being, resilience, and cultural safety. Additionally, the recommendations derived from the literature review on cultural safety education, the interwoven perspectives and the creation of the six pillars foundational for course revisions played a crucial role in guiding the project's implementation. The primary objective of this enhanced course was to foster a culture of safe and culturally sensitive care while concurrently supporting the success of students through wellness and resiliency education. The revised HCA 111 course ran from September 12th, 2022, to November 28th, 2022 and lesson plans were meticulously developed for each of the 15 classes, and post-class reflections were integrated into the plans to capture insights (see Appendix B).

Delivery of Revisions in Classes 1–8

In the first eight classes of HCA 111, we focused on exploring students' personal wellness and resiliency needs. These classes incorporated various elements, including self-assessment learning, land-based learning, Elder-led learning, and flexible content delivery. Detailed reflections on each lesson plan can be found in Appendix B.

Delivery of Pillar One: Self-awareness Learning

In the initial two classes, I focused on cultivating self-awareness, a fundamental aspect of personal growth and well-being. These sessions incorporated activities, including the wellness wheel self-assessment (Appendix C) and reflective exercises, to empower students' efforts to enhance their self-care practices. This process served as a practical tool for overall wellness improvement. Self-assessment significantly heightened students' awareness of diverse needs and perspectives, a critical step toward fostering cultural safety. This instilled appreciation and respect for diverse backgrounds, which are vital qualities for future health care professionals striving to provide inclusive and equitable care. Moreover, self-assessment profoundly impacted student resilience. By identifying growth areas and potential obstacles, students developed strategies for overcoming challenges and embraced a continuous self-improvement mindset, an indispensable trait for health care professionals.

Delivery of Pillar Two: Elder-led Learning

Elder Nina's guidance enriched the first eight classes, with a particular emphasis on self-care practices applicable to students' daily lives. The integration of indigenous teachings not only improved student well-being but also aided in managing the demands of health care education and future careers. Notably, culturally relevant self-care practices played a significant role, promoting well-being and deepening students' understanding and respect for diverse perspectives and traditions.

Delivery of Pillar Three: Land-based Learning

In Classes 2–7, students engaged in land-based learning experiences to improve mental and physical well-being. Elder Nina guided these sessions, emphasizing the importance of immersing oneself in nature and disconnecting from electronic devices. One noteworthy session, “Spirituality in Wellness” (Class 7), occurred outdoors to enhance experiential learning by encouraging students to deepen their understanding of spirituality’s role in wellness and cultural safety. Land-based learning contributed to student well-being by connecting them with nature and reinforcing resilience-building coping mechanisms. Additionally, it actively promoted cultural safety by incorporating Indigenous knowledge and emphasizing the interconnectedness of wellness, resilience, and cultural safety.

Delivery of Revisions in Classes 9-15

The revisions in Classes 1–8 prepared students to apply self-awareness and Elder-led and land-based learning in health care settings. Classes 9–15 emphasized reflection on biases, preconceptions, and worldviews to equip students for culturally safe health care service.

Delivery of Pillar Four: Community Experiential Learning

Classes 9 and 10 introduced social determinants of health and cultural safety concepts. Classes 11–15 included community-based experiential learning sessions that allowed students to reflect on the impacts of these services on community wellness and social determinants of health. Community experiential learning was pivotal for enhancing student wellness, resilience, and cultural safety. Experiences at various community organizations provided a comprehensive understanding of social determinants of health. Volunteering at the food bank, in particular, fostered a sense of purpose and heightened empathy and compassion in the students. This pillar

expanded students' knowledge and skills while nurturing their sense of social responsibility and contributing to community wellness and resilience.

Delivery of Pillar Five: Cultural Safety Education

Class 14's community presentations allowed students to propose solutions to community wellness challenges, emphasizing the importance of cultural safety in promoting community wellness and addressing health disparities. The integration of cultural safety education enriched students' understanding of diverse health care needs. The community experiential learning day and the required readings deepened students' comprehension of social determinants of health, cultural safety, and community wellness. Through these experiences, students developed insight into cultural factors that influence health outcomes, empowering them to provide equitable care tailored to diverse populations.

Delivery of Pillar Six: Flexible and Responsive Content

To enhance engagement and customize the learning experience, I introduced flexible content delivery. Five dedicated hours for assignment work were distributed across Classes 7, 8, and 13. Students verbalized that this approach reduced their stress and improved their well-being. I found that the flexible and responsive content resulted in higher-quality assignments. It also supported effective time management and skill development, nurturing student resilience and self-efficacy.

Discussion (Reflecting)

This master's level project aimed to enhance foundational knowledge and skills in wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education within Yukon University's HCA program. This objective was actualized through a comprehensive overhaul of the HCA 111 introductory course. In this discussion, the impact of the revised HCA 111 course is analyzed, drawing

insights from post-lesson evaluations (see Appendix B), and the transformative influence of the Elder-guided approach. Additionally, the effectiveness of integrating various frameworks, including the socio-ecological model, the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model, the Two-Eyed Seeing approach, and the 9 Rs is assessed. These models and approaches align with the project's overarching objectives, and the discussion concludes by offering recommendations for future research.

Obstacles to Opportunities: Challenges and Achievements in Course Delivery

The delivery of the revised HCA 111 course was marked by a series of challenges that prompted reflection and adaptation. Prior to introducing revisions, I had been teaching the course since 2018, and had established a familiar routine. The introduction of new teaching and learning approaches disrupted the routine, raising concerns about their potential impact on students' learning experiences and the overall value of the course. While the challenges were indeed real, I embraced the initial discomfort and difficulties as opportunities for growth and improvement. Navigating these course revisions required the creation of a supportive and open learning environment. Communication, at both the individual and group level, was actively encouraged to address concerns and ensure that student voices were valued. Remaining receptive to feedback and being adaptable to student preferences became paramount. Collaboration with Elder Nina played a pivotal role in infusing land-based activities and cultural safety learning into the course. Her guidance enriched the learning experience and underscored the significance of respecting and learning from Elders. Embracing these new approaches, while aligning them with course objectives, relevant literature, and leveraging Elder Nina's expertise, helped navigate uncertainties effectively. My own self-care and reflection were pivotal to my effective facilitation of course delivery.

Transformative Elements: Delivery of the Revised HCA 111 Course

In the delivery of the revised HCA 111 course, the transformative potential of land-based and Elder-led learnings became evident. Engaging students with nature and cultural wisdom led to heightened engagement, introspection, and a greater sense of belonging within our learning community. This approach, fostering connections with nature and encouraging reflection on vulnerabilities, served as a blueprint for future courses. Furthermore, early self-assessment activities, such as use of the Wellness Wheel, promoted profound self-awareness and reflection among students. These assessments guided the students to identify personal areas of growth and emphasized the role of self-care in resilience-building. Addressing sensitive topics like harm reduction and addiction in a safe and supportive environment was a priority. Incorporating Elder-led learning and a land-based approach deepened understanding, preparing students for the challenges they may encounter in health care.

Our community experiential learning day highlighted the tangible impact of their studies and strengthened students' ties to their community, fostering a sense of social responsibility. Additionally, the cultural safety component empowered students to shift perspectives and commit to enhancing community health and wellness. By integrating self-awareness, cultural understanding, and community engagement, I observed profound transformation in students' attitudes and a genuine commitment to positive community change.

Indigenous Elder Teachings: Elder Nina's Integral Role in Nurturing Self-Care, Land-Based Learning, and Cultural Safety

Elder Nina played a pivotal role in introducing students to a diverse range of self-care techniques that spanned multiple dimensions—mental, physical, spiritual, environmental, and communal. Students verbalized that these practices could be integrated into their daily routines

because of the in-class exposure, providing them with practical tools to address immediate and ongoing challenges that necessitated self-care. Elder Nina's teachings encompassed mindfulness exercises, grounding techniques, and land-based practices that resulted in enhanced self-awareness, supported mental and physical health, and bolstered resilience—attributes poised to benefit students throughout their health care education and future careers. The incorporation of land-based learning experiences yielded significant benefits, even in adverse weather conditions. Students consistently found outdoor sessions highly conducive to self-care practices. Engaging in these activities multiple times and gaining proficiency in the techniques learned in class substantially enhanced their overall well-being.

The land-based setting allowed students to deepen their connection with the natural environment, leading to a renewed sense of vitality. Engaging in physical activity, savoring fresh air, and immersing themselves in nature equipped students with essential coping mechanisms for their future roles in health care, effectively nurturing their resilience. In addition to personal development, the integration of Indigenous knowledge and traditions, guided by Elder Nina, had a substantial impact on promoting cultural safety. This exposure elevated students' cultural competence and fostered a deeper understanding of the significance of cultural safety in health care, thereby enriching their overall educational experience.

Enhancing Health Education Programs Through the Use of Inclusive and Comprehensive Frameworks

The integration of the socio-ecological model, the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model, the Two-Eyed Seeing approach, and the 9 Rs in the context of the HCA 111 course revision at Yukon University presents a promising process for advancing health education programs.

Cultural Safety

The incorporation of Indigenous perspectives, land-based practices, and education on cultural safety learning aligns with the growing recognition of the importance of cultural safety in nursing practice. Health education students who receive education rooted in these principles are better equipped to provide culturally safe care to diverse patient populations, including Indigenous communities.

Inclusive and Comprehensive Frameworks

The socio-ecological model and the First Nations perspective on health and wellness model offer comprehensive frameworks that encompass various facets of health care. This can help ensure that health education students are well-rounded and prepared to address the complex and multifaceted challenges of modern health care. In an era when health care is evolving to address diverse patient needs and health care disparities, an approach that integrates cultural safety, wellness, and Indigenous perspectives is not only relevant but also aligns with contemporary health care trends and best practices.

Preparation for Real-World Challenges

Addressing issues like Indigenous-specific racism and discrimination, ensures that health education students are better prepared to navigate the challenges they may encounter in the health care field and ensuring they will have the knowledge and skills to advocate for equitable and culturally safe care. In summary, the integration of these models and principles into health education courses and curriculums holds great promise for preparing health education students to become safe, resilient, and compassionate health care professionals. Health education programs can better align their curricula with the evolving needs of the health care field and promote positive outcomes for both students and the patients they will serve.

Recommendations for Future Research

The master's level project discussed in this paper has made significant strides in enhancing wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education within the HCA program at Yukon University. It addressed crucial issues facing HCAs, including caregiver burnout and Indigenous-specific racism and discrimination. Given the scope of this project, it is important to continue this work and promote safer interactions within the healthcare system. Below are recommendations for future research to promote a culturally safe, sustainable HCA workforce amidst the challenges confronting the Yukon healthcare system.

Long-term Impact Assessment

While the project's immediate outcomes are promising, future research should focus on conducting a long-term assessment of the impact of the revisions. This would involve tracking wellness and resiliency, along with the performance and cultural safety of HCA graduates and measuring changes in health care outcomes within Indigenous communities. A longitudinal study would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the sustained impact of the project.

Generalizability Studies

To expand the reach and applicability of the project's findings, researchers could conduct studies to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of similar revisions in other health care education programs or institutions. Comparative research across various settings would help identify best practices and adaptability.

Comprehensive Evaluation Methods

While student evaluations provide valuable insights, future research should consider incorporating a broader range of evaluation methods. This could include assessments of

graduates' competencies, feedback from health care employers, and measuring the impact of culturally safe care on patient outcomes.

Knowledge Translation

To effectively translate the knowledge from this project, a comprehensive strategy should be employed. This strategy involves engaging key stakeholders within the Yukon healthcare system, including healthcare administrators, educators, and policymakers, through presentations and tailored workshops. Additionally, reaching out to Indigenous communities in the Yukon is essential to align cultural safety education efforts with their needs, fostering trust and collaboration through consultations and community engagement. Academic dissemination through conferences is vital for reaching educators and researchers. Potential conferences include the Canadian Association of Schools of Nursing annual conference, the Canadian Association of Continuing Care Educators annual conference, and the International Congress on Circumpolar Health. Journal submissions would further serve to move the momentum of this project further into academia and health care settings. Potential journals include *The Northern Review*, *International Journal of Circumpolar Health*, and the *Canadian Journal of Nursing Leadership*.

Ultimately, by effectively communicating the significance and impact of course revisions, this project aims to contribute to the creation of a culturally safe and resilient healthcare workforce, addressing the urgent needs of Indigenous health care recipients and promoting safer healthcare environments in the Yukon and beyond.

Conclusion

This project successfully enriched and enhanced the knowledge related to wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education for students in the HCA program at Yukon University. By revising the HCA 111 course, the project aimed to prepare students for success as front-line

caregivers and address pressing cultural safety needs in the Yukon healthcare system. The project incorporated six fundamental pillars of self-awareness learning, Elder-led learning, land-based learning, community experiential learning, cultural safety education, and flexible and responsive content delivery to provide a comprehensive and culturally responsive educational experience.

Utilizing an AI methodology, the project built upon the strengths of the existing course, fostering a positive and empowering environment for students and educators. The inclusion of Indigenous and interwoven perspectives and engagement with a local Elder ensured cultural relevance and authenticity. Evidence-based strategies informed the revisions, increasing the likelihood of positive outcomes. The student-centred approach, combined with self-assessment, experiential learning, and flexible content delivery, catered to the unique needs of HCA students, and promoted their well-being, engagement, and success. The positive student feedback validated the effectiveness of the revisions in promoting student well-being, resilience, and cultural safety. However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of the project, such as limited generalizability and the need for long-term assessment.

This project contributes to the ongoing efforts in healthcare education and practice by fostering reconciliation and meaningful changes in the healthcare system. By equipping HCA students with necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes, the revised course addresses caregiver burnout and Indigenous-specific racism and discrimination, and, ultimately, enhances the quality of care provided to Yukon Indigenous healthcare recipients. Overall, this project demonstrates the value of integrating wellness, resiliency, and cultural safety education in healthcare programs. By prioritizing the holistic well-being of students and promoting cultural competence,

the project advances the goals of creating a safe, inclusive, and equitable healthcare system for all.

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Appendix A

North2North Northern European Trip

North2north Northern European Network Trip

Name: Samantha Piper

Institute: Yukon University

Department: Health, Education, and Human Services

Section 1: Overall Experience

Please provide a brief paragraph or two about your overall experience as a delegate on the n2n Network Trip.

As a delegate with the n2n Network trip, I had the opportunity for valuable engagement with northern partners. This included the partners across northern Canada as well as Scandinavia. Getting to know the delegates from northern Canada was enlightening and engaging and provided opportunity to discuss shared challenges and opportunities unique to the North.

The travel across northern Scandinavia was invaluable to my perspectives on teaching in the north. I learned new approaches to the unique challenges of teaching within Northern Health Programs and how resourcing can be allocated in different ways. These new perspectives will prove very helpful to future planning within healthcare programs at YukonU. I would be interested in returning to one or more Scandinavian Universities to learn more about the specifics of their programming.

Section 2: Institutional Visits

Overview: *Please provide information on what meetings you attended and 3 to 5 high level bullet points consisting of key takeaways from your visit to the institution. We ask that you please highlight which departments you met with at the institution and do you see a potential for exchange with that institute (please provide a brief statement of why or why not an exchange could work). This report is meant to be brief and very high-level information, Faye and Erica may be reaching out at a later date to ask for more information during their final report writing process. Thank you for your time in advance.*

UiT Arctic University of Norway (Alta, Norway)

Key takeaways:

- UiT has fantastic opportunities for exchange of students and staff. They have many programs and departments, but limited options for courses offered in English (barrier for Canadian Students).
- Dr. Greta Mehus discussed the nursing program and noted the inclusion of traditional healing as well as research regarding the essential inclusion of culture within health programming and delivery.

Which departments did you meet with, and do you see an opportunity for exchange moving forward?

Departments:

- Dr. Greta Mehus – The nursing program

Potential for Exchange:

- Currently limited exchange opportunities between YukonU health programs and UiT due to the short programs offered at YukonU and the differences in program layouts. If YukonU creates health science degrees, partnership would be beneficial due to UiT conducting research in rural and remote nursing as well as traditional healing. Specific opportunity with year 4 of the UiT program relating to the 8 week practicum of Nursing leadership in the healthcare facilities. Potential for staff exchange.

Sámi University of Applied Sciences (Kautokeino, Norway)

Key takeaways:

- **The focus on the Sami peoples and culture was incredible.** Aimed at providing knowledge and education in Northern Sami language
- In Kautokeino, elementary school is also taught in Northern Sami language
- They have undergrad, masters and PhD in Sami education
- Sami traditional knowledge is included
- Elders are utilized in teacher education as knowledge holders. The elders are accepted as knowledge holders without needing an advanced degree. UArctic is working on considering of applying traditional knowledge holders as holding advanced knowledge.

Which departments did you meet with, and do you see an opportunity for exchange moving forward?

Departments:

- Teacher education program for primary school
- Teacher education program for early childhood (Laila Anutti)
- Social Sciences (Louisa)
- Sami Pathfinder program
- Program on Indigenous Language and literature
- Dr. Greta Mehus on Sami Nurse Education Program

Potential for Exchange:

- Bachelor and master's programs in indigenous journalism (open to international students)
- Limited further exchange options due to most courses being taught in the Northern Sami language.

Sámi Institute of Education (Inari, Finland)

Key takeaways:

- Specialized curriculum with focus on Northern Sami language and culture (and reindeer husbandry)
- This remote institution noted that people who are educated in the region tend to stay in that region while “outsiders” tend to stay short terms then leave
- Arctic nursing partnership with Oulu. Nursing program highlighted the need for more indigenous based nursing education. A program was designed to have a more education on culture and language for healthcare delivery to Sami people. This resulted in the program length being extended by 6 months as it was not possible to have all of this relevant information added to the already full program.

Which departments did you meet with, and do you see an opportunity for exchange moving forward?

Departments:

- No individual meetings

Potential for Exchange:

- Sami Institute will be starting an English speaking tourism program. That is a potential if YukonU develops tourism specific programs.
- Nursing – No current opportunities as the focus is Sami language of instruction. However, YukonU would benefit from engaging in the work on sustainable nursing in the circumpolar north. <https://www.uarctic.org/news/2021/2/call-for-applications-field-school-on-sustainable-nursing-in-the-circumpolar-north/>

University of Applied Science/Lapland University (Rovaniemi, Finland)

Key takeaways:

Teacher Education Meeting

- University of the arctic – teacher education for social justice and diversity (20 members)
- UNESCO – United National Educational, Scientific and Cultural organization/UNITWIN – Network on Teacher Education and Social Justice and diversity in Education (around 50 members)
- YukonU has the option to join either network. The UArctic threshold is quite low to join. The UNESCO group is harder to join as there is a once-a-year administrative meeting to join.
- Inclusive education – definition is quite broad and includes an understanding the need for the best education for everybody, this is why it is linked to social justice.
- Online and rural education and indigenous education are components.
- Looking at a model of having the “Arctic 5 Education” Universities together for a shared course with a one week workshop together
- Post-grad cultural education for teachers from elsewhere
- More traditional story telling and land-based education. Finland finds that there is a lack of teaching materials for teaching Sami language. One instructor at University of Lapland is producing research and summaries of teaching approaches through the Sami cultural context.
- Expert lectures and help have been made available to existing teachers to help them have more cultural inclusion and capacity of applying cultural information.

Nursing

- 3.5 years to get nursing degree, then 1.5 year masters
- Was able to move away from national nursing regulation to make their own programming. In Finland, each institution may create their own program. Graduates can work across EU
- Difficulty with English program because hospital did not want to take English speaking students
VR is used for communication practice of language skills. VR technology programming comes from Lapland University of Applied Science – contact Marita Turulin for more information.
- Full time study counsellor for the program who keeps in constant touch with students and follows-up (study counsellor). They only have a 6% attrition rate... The instructors notify the study counsellor who follows up with the students.
- Students in practicum have an instructor for the first day, then follow-up phone calls and evaluation, otherwise, nurses working on the floor take on the student. The University pays the institution for the nurses to take students (the money can go to the institution [administration] or the nurse depending on the preference of the institution).

Social Work

- Universities are autonomous in Finland, so they have established a university network for social work for coordination with 6 Universities
- Finland offers specialization in SW with a master's degree. 2.5 years part-time.
- They have doctoral studies and programs in all 6 partner institutions
- Some virtual courses are shared between the 6 campuses. 15-20 courses per year shared. Most of the course are at the masters level to allow those with specialized knowledge to teach to groups with specific interests despite the community that they live in.
- New Finnish legislation states that SW caseload cannot exceed 35 child protection clients. SW have more coordination and bureaucratic roles vs therapy. Lots of legal studies included in the education.
- Scheduling is flexible and teachers can independently decide meeting times (evenings and weekends too)
- An extensive part of the studies consists of research

Which departments did you meet with, and do you see an opportunity for exchange moving forward?

Departments:

- Teacher Education
- Nursing
- Social Work

Potential for Exchange:

- Yes, certainly with teacher education programs. It seems as though it may differ year to year what is offered in English. Nice focus on culture, tradition, and language.
- Yes, in Kemi, there is a nursing program in English.
- International students have more times on campus to allow more time for teaching Finnish cultural norms

- There would be potential for exchange for SW students

University of Oulu (Oulu, Finland)

Key takeaways:

- **Nursing** - Program layout includes over half in virtual with a lot of independent work. When students come to campus there is mostly hands-on (skills lab)
- **Social Services** - Learning and teaching philosophy – Students need to read and learn and study prior to application. Teachers are advisors and mentors.
- 2 weeks spent on orientation – learn to learn (tutoring, getting to know study groups, etc).
- Study groups are created to create relationships and communication
 - Most courses run over 8 weeks.
 - A semester is cut in half (8 weeks), then if students need more time, they have the additional 8 weeks.

Which departments did you meet with, and do you see an opportunity for exchange moving forward?

Departments:

- Nursing (Ms Virpi Makikangas, Virpi.makikangas@oamk.fi)
- Social services (physiotherapy, OT, and social work)
-

Potential for Exchange:

- Currently, nursing students do not engage in north to north (lack of information/partnership). Nursing students could complete clinical in English as most instructors have some English.
- Social Services - There are some courses in English for exchange students.

Luleå University of Technology (Lulea, Sweden)

Key takeaways:

Nursing and Health:

- Future research interests include northern indigenous education
- Partnership with the robotics lab for sensor technology for seniors living alone
- Nursing PhD is taught in English
- Sweden has a lack of teachers, so the model has been distance education for a while. Students come in for one to two weeks per term, otherwise online
- Each semester is divided into two
- Nursing has been teaching distance for 30 years
- Teach for Sweden – Teacher educator program for people teaching in the classroom as a compliment for leadership. They have the education part of teaching, then 1.5 years of school. For example, a bachelors of science, then 1.5 years education to become a teacher

- Health departments have lots of partnerships with robotics (human mobility science lab, human health and activity lab).
- “The Importance of nature for health” – one of their research projects

Educational Research – Focusing on the Arctic and Indigenous People

- Eva Alderby (Also works with UIT in Norway)
- Theme of education within the Arctic 5 collaboration
- Online Courses on Master level: Arctic Inclusive Education (3 modules) – Taught in English
- YukonU should join the thematic network on Teacher Education for Social Justice and Diversity in Education through UActic – different chapters from different countries
 - Program – DistARCTIC – rural education
 - Arctic Children – Development and Research project of Psychosocial Well-being of children and youth in the arctic (2008)
 - Desert and Ice 0 Learning without Boundaries (A research and development project of learning between Northern Sweden and Southern Australia)
 - Research with children asked to make drawing of where they learn – children drew land and culture – noted in book “Voices from the Margins” – Eva Alderby

Which departments did you meet with, and do you see an opportunity for exchange moving forward?

Departments:

- Health, Education and Technology – Maria Larsson-Lund/Eva Lindgren (OT department)
- Nursing specific program – Paivi Juuso
- Educational Research

Potential for Exchange:

- The language of nursing education is not English, but due to the research and work currently underway, ongoing partnerships with the intent of exchange for staff would prove beneficial. Exchange with nursing students would be limited for PN students due to differing layout and language of instruction of programming.
- Educational programming is more geared towards staff exchange as the English speaking courses are at the Masters Level.

Nord University (Bodø, Norway)

Key takeaways:

Faculty of Social Services

- Bodo campus has SW
- Research on welfare and social relations, history, culture and media
- Research and partnership with circumpolar studies
- Many courses in English for international students (many circumpolar studies)
- Some English circumpolar courses are offered asynch online
- Opening a new center for sami and indigenous studies – teaches south sami and lulea language

Nursing Meeting

- Study locations (Vesteralen, Bodo, Halgeland, Namsos and Levanger)
- Lots of teaching and learning online
- Educate 500-600 new nurses each year
- Bodo has been educating nurses for over 100 years
- 50% of the program in clinical
- Focused clinicals include: home care, nursing homes, medical practice (hospital), mental health, leadership administration (final practicum where students choose their locations), surgical (post-surgical). 50% of the practicum is regulated by EU.
- Culture and language of Sami people is included, but not too much.
- Crisis training in Bodo "Ovelse Nord/Exercise North" every year

Which departments did you meet with, and do you see an opportunity for exchange moving forward?

Departments:

- Faculty of Social Services
- Nursing Department

Potential for Exchange:

- SW program has English taught courses and exchange potential. Primary exchange opportunity is for practicum.
- Limited possibilities for Yukon U student exchanges due to no Bachelor of Science degree in health or nursing provided from YukonU. Most programming is taught in Norwegian.

Appendix B

Lesson Plans

HCA 111: Class 1

In-Person **Sept 12, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

This half-day session provides an overview of HCA 111. It will allow for the exploration of class layouts, expectations, assignments and introductions to course concepts.

Materials and supplies

- **Course and Assignment Outlines**
- **Activity workbook**
- **Course textbook (Brene Brown's Gifts of Imperfection)**

Printed Items

- **Course and Assignment Outlines**

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- Describe how one's ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 1

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- understand the course description and purpose and know the location of course documents.
- have a deeper understanding of the assignments of HCA 111 and the corresponding dates of these assignments.
- understand the expectations attached to the class readings.
- receive a general introduction to their wellness journey and evaluate their overall wellness using the Wellness Wheel.
- reflect on their understanding of self-awareness and practical interventions towards resiliency.
- Identify an aspect of their completed wellness wheel that they would like to work on through HCA 111.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
9:00 – 9:15	Introduction to HCA 111 (LOA 1)	<p><i>*Email participants prior to the course:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reminder about class date and time</i> <p>Supplies required include printed course outline, assignment outline, and course planner for due dates.</p> <p>HANDOUTS: a course outline, an assignment outline, a journal, and an empty name card as they enter the class. Ask students to write their name and identify their preferred pronoun on the card.</p> <p>Facilitator speaking (Introduce course and timeline)</p>	Students receive course materials and prepare their name card for the table.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome students into the classroom. - Introduce myself. - Start PowerPoint and move to the slide on the “Class Objective”. Review this page, then move to the “Course Documents”. Show students the HCA 111 Moodle page and review where to find information. - Have students 	
9:15-9:30 am	Assignment review (LOA 2)	<p>Small group discussions: Now we are going to review the assignments outline. Count off from 1-3 (students count off), then split into your 3 groups. Each group will review one of the course assignments.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group 1 - Journal • Group 2 – Personal Wellness Plan • Group 3 – Community Wellness Challenge <p>ASK: Prepare an outline to explain this assignment to the class. Tell us the important dates when these assignments are due and the weight of each assignment to the course total.</p>	<p>Think, pair, share</p> <p>Each student group will present</p> <p>Students can review the assignments and write down the due dates.</p>
9:30 – 9:35	Readings review (LOA 3)	<p>Readings Expectations: Each class, there are assigned readings and optional resources. For Classes 1-8, the readings will be from “Gifts of Imperfection” by Brene Brown. Classes 9-14 will also have mandatory assigned readings. Each class will also have optional readings and resources found on Moodle. For each mandatory reading, the following format will be expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For each week’s reading you will prepare a list: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 Key Points from the reading - 2 New things learned - 1 Question that you have <p>These will be reviewed at the beginning of each class and are an expectation for each week.</p> <p>Review guidelines for appropriate classroom disclosure</p>	
9:35-10:00	Introduction to wellness (LOA 4)	<p>Group Discussion</p> <p>Written reflection and group sharing: Wellness 4 prompts- quadrants (free write – 1 min/quadrant):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is wellness? • How is it different than health? • What do you need to be well? • What would you like to learn more about? <p>Video: “Are Health and Wellness Really Related?” (2:41)</p> <p>PowerPoint presentation on the FNHA First Nations Perspective of Wellness (slides6-7).</p>	Group discussion and personal reflections
10:00 – 10:15	Break	Elder Nina Bolton will join the class	

10:15-11:00 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Reflection and the Wellness Wheel (LOA 4)	<p>Slide 8: “The strength within”. Provide students an opportunity to learn about reflection and the skills that they bring to the class and the field of health care.</p> <p>“Your Wellness Journey” (Slides 9-12) <i>Where do you want to go and how will you get there?</i></p> <p>Wellness Wheel Introduction (Slides 13-15) What are your unique wellness needs? The 8 quadrants include: significant other, culture & tradition, nurturing spirit, physical health, fun & recreation, career satisfaction, stress management, family & friends. Provide overview of each section and have students follow along in their journals.</p>	Students offer thoughts and reflections
11:00-11:15 am	Wellness Wheel Activity (LO4)	<p>Wellness Wheel Activity (Slides 16 – 17)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students will in their wellness wheels. Students are informed that the information from this activity will be foundational for the assignments in the classroom. 	Individual time to fill in the wellness wheel
11:15-11:40 pm	Wellness Wheel Reflection (LO5 & LO6) Provide course feedback	<p>Individual reflection Go to the wellness wheel activity Look at the quadrant- <i>What does my wellness look like right now?</i> Reflect: <i>Which quadrants of the wellness wheel need the most attention?</i> Identify an aspect of their completed wellness wheel that they would like to work on through HCA 111</p> <p>Pair or Group brainstorm- on paper or board <i>What have you learned about your own wellness needs?</i></p> <p>Mention University resources: Counselling, campus gym and weight room, Roddy’s Camp, Harry Allen Lounge, the classroom.</p>	Identify an aspect of their completed wellness wheel that they would like to work on through HCA 111 – Students will write this down
11:40 – 11:50	Introduction to stress, resiliency, delegation, self-care, and SMART goals	<p>Review slides 18-24 Discuss how identification of areas of need through the wellness wheel activity will allow for SMART goal creation and implementation through the course.</p>	
11:50 – 11:55	Homework and Exit ticket	<p>Review homework:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Gifts of Imperfection</i> Page 1-21 – Prepare the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format - Wellness Journal Submission #1 – Due next class - One self-care act that will be implemented - Bring a 5-minute de-stressor activity idea to next class and explain why it is helpful for overall wellness. <p>Exit ticket: One activity that you would like included in this course</p>	

Reflection: Class 1 went well. The timing was great. Nina joined the class at 10 am and the students responded very well to her. Students expressed lots of great reflections as we worked through the self-assessment activities. The wellness wheel self-assessment was new for all the students. We took time during the class to complete the wellness wheel self-assessments. The class time was essential for this activity because many of the students had questions about the assessment and how best to answer the questions. A few students mentioned that their wellness

wheels looked sad and that these brought up tough feelings for them. These feelings were validated, and I shared that the whole class is starting from a place of self-awareness and that for resiliency to form, we need to know what needs we have as humans. Students were encouraged to reflect on their identified areas of need and think about a wellness plan to address an area that they wanted to work on.

HCA 111: Class 2

In-Person **Sept 16, 2022, 1:00 p.m. – 4:00 p.m.**

This half-day session introduces students to land-based mindfulness, self-awareness as a tool of resiliency, the transtheoretical model for change, and greater awareness of how they spend their time.

Materials and supplies	Printed Items
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handouts: Mindfulness activity, self-awareness activity, Stages of Change Activity • Course textbook (Brene Brown's Gifts of Imperfection) 	Mindfulness activity, self-awareness activity, Stages of Change Activity

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one's ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 2

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Participate in a land-based mindfulness activity.
- II. Reflect on their self-awareness following mindfulness and reflect on this as a tool of resiliency.
- III. Develop an awareness of their personal self-care strategies.
- IV. Learn about the Transtheoretical Model for change and learn to apply this knowledge to their wellness journey.
- V. Develop greater self-awareness through self-assessments.
- VI. Develop skills for identifying how they spend their time.

CLASS PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
1300 – 1320	Land-based activity (LOA 1)	<p><i>*Email participants prior to the course:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reminder about bringing outside clothing and shoes</i> <p>Welcome students into the classroom.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Orient students to the fact that we will take part in a short walk outside. Students will leave their belongings in the locked classroom. Students will be asked to bring their wellness planners on the walk along with a pen or pencil. - Hand out Mindfulness Activity worksheet. Students may write on the sheet or use the sheet to guide what they write in their journals. - We will take a short walk outside through the woods. Students will be asked not to talk once we start on the trail. Rather, students will 	Walk outside

		<p>be encouraged to listen. We will stop about 2 minutes into the walk and students will be asked to find a comfortable position (standing or sitting) and breath.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instructor will guide students through 3 cycles of breath work, then have students reflect in silence for 1 minute. - At the end of one minute, students will be asked to write down 5 things they see, 4 things they feel, 3 things they hear, 2 things they smell, 1 thing they taste, and one thing they are grateful for. - The whole group will then return to the classroom 	
1320-1340	Reflection review (LOA 2)	<p>Small group discussions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students will split into groups of 2-3 • Students will reflect on their self-awareness following mindfulness and reflect on this as a tool of resiliency. Students will have 5 minutes for this discussion <p>ASK: Please report your general reflections to the larger group</p>	<p>Think, pair, share</p> <p>Each student group will present</p>
1340 - 1410	Review of homework (LOA 3)	<p>Classroom discussion regarding assigned reading and activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss your 5-minute de-stressor activity idea (homework from last class) • Discuss the readings from Gifts of Imperfection in the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format <p>Review guidelines for appropriate classroom disclosure</p>	Students reflect on their readings
1410 - 1425		<p>Instructor Presentation</p> <p>PowerPoint presentation on the “love and Joy” list (slides3-4).</p>	Students will write their individual “love and Joy” lists
1425 - 1440	Break		
1440 - 1500	Models of Change (LOA 4)	<p>Slide 5: “Yes, you can”. Students will watch a short video from the 2016 RIO Paralympics (5:30). The purpose of this is to have students reflect on what individuals see as barriers to wellness and to reflect on how these can be overcome.</p> <p>Models of Change (Slides 6-8) Review the Transtheoretical Model as a model of change. Show the clip on “Improve Your Life Using the Stages of Change” (4:50) to highlight the model. Have students offer thought on where they are in terms of a change they are working to make in their life (such as going to school) as examples of stages.</p> <p>Stages of Change Activity (5 minutes) Groups of 3, identify the stages of the sentences. Once complete, identify where they might be in their own change process</p>	<p>Students offer thoughts and reflections.</p> <p>Stages of Change Activity (5 minutes) Groups of 3, identify the stages of the sentences. Once complete, identify where they might be in their own change process</p>

1500 - 1530	Self-awareness Activities (LO5 & LO6)	Who Are You (Slides 10 – 15) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students will write their answers to the questions on the screen with slides 10 – 16. Hand out the “Weeklong inventory of “daily time and habits homework” sheet. This sheet will have all the questions from the slides and will highlight the homework assignment. - Slide 10, recommend that students write the things that immediately come to their minds with each question. Short and quick answers. - Slide 11 – 15, Students can take more time to answer these questions for themselves. 	Individual time to write down answers to the questions regarding self-assessments. These are not shared with the class.
1530 - 1535	Homework self-awareness activity (LO5 & LO6)	Review of homework activity (Slides 16-17) <i>“For the next week, you will record your days. Try and record these in the same place (a journal) This will give you the opportunity to get used to the journals and really assess where you spend your time.”</i> This activity will provide the foundation for the personal wellness plan activity	
1535- 1555	Reflection on vulnerability and shame	Slide 18 Clips from Brene Brown’s Ted talks on Vulnerability (6 minutes – play from 14:01) and shame (12 minutes – play from 8:20)	
1555 – 1600	Homework and Exit ticket	Review homework: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Gifts of Imperfection Pages 23-54 Prepare the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format.</i> – Weeklong inventory of “daily time and habits” – this is the background information needed for the Personal Wellness Plan Exit ticket: 1 thing you liked from today and 1 thing you would like to do differently	

Reflection:

The land-based activity went very well. Timing of the class went well. Nina was unable to join class, so I completed the first land-based activity on my own.

The **Who Are You** activity creates awareness for the students to identify their limiting beliefs and create a foundation for the personal wellness plan. The activity was well received. The activity is a precursor to a homework assignment that the students complete called the weeklong inventory of “daily time and habits”. The in-class self-assessment and the homework create a foundation of awareness for students to identify how they spend their time and to allow them to identify the potential opportunities for how they can spend their time in more healthy, focused, and mindful ways.

For next time, additional instructor support would be of benefit. One student became very emotional following the land-based activity. The nature of self-awareness and reflection creates the potential that students may struggle with the feelings that come up for them. I found it challenging to be able to continue to instruct the class while providing individualized support.

HCA 111: Class 3

In-Person **Sept 26, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

This class dives into the concepts of sleep and stress and works to focus on the importance of these topics on resiliency and wellness.

Materials and supplies

- Activity workbook

Printed Items

- “What’s on your plate?” Activity

- **Course textbook (Brene Brown’s Gifts of Imperfection)**
- **“Your balance map” Activity**

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.
- Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 3

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- Participate in guided meditation.
- Develop an understanding of the value of mindfulness and meditation as evidence-based stress reduction and resiliency building tools.
- Reflect on how they spend their time as identified in the “daily time and habits” activity.
- Develop awareness areas in their life where small changes can result in enhanced wellness and resiliency.
- Develop further awareness of their personal self-care strategies.
- Learn about the importance of sleep on wellness and resiliency.
- Learn practical approaches to stress management.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
9:00 – 9:20 am	Introduction to guided mediation (LOA 1)	Supplies required include blank paper for in-class activities. Welcome students into the classroom. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome students into the classroom. Invite students to get comfortable in their seats in preparation for a 10-minute guided mediation. Request that students put away electronic devices to prevent distraction. Start the mediation – the instructor will model the desired participation by taking place in the activity. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZToicYcHIQU Following the meditation, students are thanked for their participation and asked to share any reflections that are present for them 	Guided mediation
9:20-10:00 am	Review of homework (LOA 3, 4 &6)	Instructor Presentation (PP Slide 3) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Having the slide present helps students to remember what they need to include in their discussion.</i> Classroom discussion regarding assigned reading and activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gifts of Imperfection reflections in the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format. Weeklong inventory of “daily time and habits” – reflections of time spent and time available. 	Students will each take a turn to share their reflections and thoughts from the readings and homework assignment.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List 3 ways online time helping, and 3 ways online time is hindering your time management. <p><i>The purpose of the “daily time and habits” activity is to help students identify where they might be able to modify “time wasting” activities (ex: social media, television, etc) into time for resiliency building activities. This activity also serves as a resource for their personal wellness plans because it helps students identify how much time they devote to activities that negatively impact their resiliency. This is where students often start their personal wellness plans because they can see where changes are needed.</i></p> <p><i>Weekly reflection on the assigned readings enhances student engagement with the readings and it promotes group building through having students share their reflections and thoughts. It helps instructors build relevant content into future classes by diving deeper into the concepts that students bring up during these reflections.</i></p>	
10:00 – 10:15	Break	Elder Nina Bolton to join the class	
10:15-10:35 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Sleep (LOA 6)	<p>Slide 4: Watch a TedEd video on “The Benefits of a good night’s sleep” (5:44)</p> <p>Students reflect on the following questions while watching the video:</p> <p><i>Consider your healthy habits journal from the last week... List your barriers to a good night sleep Do you use your phone in bed within the last hour before sleep? Do you have a regular sleep schedule? Does your mind keep you awake at night? Have you tried meditation to help with this?</i></p> <p>Slide 4/5: Review the impacts of poor sleep on the body and discuss how to enhance sleep.</p>	Students offer thoughts and reflections
10:35-10:50 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Stress (LOA 4, 5, & 7)	<p>Presentation on Stress (PP Slides 7 - 14)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Instructor discusses stress, stressor, eustress and distress and discusses the general adaptation syndrome phases of alarm, resistance, and exhaustion. Show TedEd on “How stress can make you sick” (4:42) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v-t1Z5-oPtU&list=PLJicmE8fK0Ei7nZRhCz2zjNgt-NYPUk1a&index=8 Slides include discussion on “Stressors” (Slide 13), and Stress Management (Slide 14). Speak in depth on slide 14 about how self-reflection and mindfulness can aid with stress management. 	Students list their own eustressors and distressors. Prompting questions: Why do they affect some people differently? Can you change a distressor in to a eustressor? How could you accomplish that?
10:50-11:30 pm	PowerPoint Presentation on Stress (LOA 4, 5, & 7)	<p>Stress management self-reflection activities (PP 15 – 19) and presentation on stress</p> <p>Slide 15 introduces the “The Warning Signs Continuum”. This model assists students to self-identify stressors and their mental wellness. This model will also be used in future classes.</p>	Students will complete the following:

	Provide course feedback	<p>http://tandfbis.s3.amazonaws.com/rt-media/pp/common/sample-chapters/9780415897907.pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“We need to gain a better understanding of our own warning signs along the continuum of compassion fatigue. Using traffic lights as an analogy, the green zone is where you are when you are at your very best (I sometimes joke that you are only in the green zone when you’ve been in the field for 2 weeks or when you have just returned from a 5-month yoga retreat in Tahiti). The yellow zone is where most of us live most of the time. We have warning signs emerging but we often ignore them. The red zone is the danger zone. The far end of the red zone finds us on stress leave, clinically depressed or totally withdrawn from others and wracked with anxiety.” (Mathieu, 2012, p. 48).</i> http://tandfbis.s3.amazonaws.com/rt-media/pp/common/sample-chapters/9780415897907.pdf - <i>While we are not specifically talking about compassion fatigue in today’s class, this is a very important topic in the conversation about self-awareness and resiliency.</i> - <i>Instructor can add in additional information from Chapter 6 of “The Compassion Fatigue Workbook”. Page 59 – 60 provide details for creating a personalized “Self-care wellness dosimeter”</i> <p>Slide 16 – “What’s on your plate”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students will work through this activity on a blank sheet of paper. This activity requires about 7 minutes. <p>Slide 17/18 – “Your Balance Map”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guide students through the activity. Students will use another piece of paper to create a balance map for themselves by outlining the most important aspect of their personal wellness at the bottom, then 3 additional pieces in order of importance (the most important on the bottom). <p>Slide 19 – Time management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students can review and reflect regarding: What things took up the most time? The least time? What are your “time wasters”? How could you better manage your time? <p>Slide 20 – “Taming the Technostress”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review the slide to point out how students can better utilize technology (3 minutes) <p>Slide 21 – “Learning Time Management”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review slide and watch the video (5:05) on “Stress Management Strategies: Ways to Unwind” 	<p>“What’s on your plate?” “Your balance map”</p> <p>Students will reflect on the powerpoint slides</p>
11:30 – 11:42	Group activity (LOA 4, 5, & 7)	<p>Student group activity “Problems to Possibilities”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Person A - Talk for a few minutes about something that is a stressor for you - Person B - Craft a question that leads person A to reframe the challenge/problem into a possibility - Switch – Person B talks and person A listens then crafts a questions that leads person B to reframe the challenge/problem into a possibility 	<p>Think, pair, share. Groups of 2. Students choose a stressor that they have some control over for the activity. Person B requires promoting to help</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Let your “support person” know if their question was or was not helpful and why <p>The purpose of this is to have students support each other to reframe their stressors</p>	them reframe the challenge into a possibility.
11:42 – 11:57	Video (LOA 7) Guided meditation and grounding with Nina	<p>Video from Kelly McGonigal on “How to make stress your friend” (14:16)</p> <p>Nina Bolton guided the students through a First Nations focused grounding activity. The activity took about 10 minutes and the students stood, close their eyes, then were guided to ground their feet with mother earth, stretch their hands to father sky, then provide a protective bubble around themselves.</p>	
11:57 – 12:00	Homework and Exit ticket	<p>Review homework:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Gifts of Imperfection</i> as outlined in Moodle - Wellness Journal Submission #2 	

Reflection: Add “The Compassion Fatigue Workbook” to the course required text list. It is very helpful to many aspects of this course.

The class went well, mostly. We had an unexpected moment where a student had an allergic reaction to a food that a co-student brought to class. The allergy happened close to break, so a fellow colleague sat with the student while we continued class. At break, we moved class to a new location and wiped down the previous room.

Class itself was good, but I would appreciate having another text that could help to support students with the activities in class. Students enjoyed the “Problems to possibilities” activity. Several students required some prompting to choose a problem that they have some control over. The partner required promoting to help their partner to reframe the challenge into a possibility.

Having Nina present was wonderful. The activity that she offered at the end was very well received and so practical. I assigned watching the video for homework.

HCA 111: Class 4

In-Person **Sept 29, 2022, 1:00 p.m. – 4:00 p.m.**

This class dives into the concepts of physical health and diet and works to focus on the importance of these topics on resiliency and wellness.

Materials and supplies

- Activity workbook
- Course textbook (Brene Brown’s *Gifts of Imperfection*)

Printed Items

- None

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 4

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Participate in a land-based activity.
- II. Develop an understanding of the value of resiliency training for sustainable careers in health care.
- III. Students will develop a SMART goal for change that they would like to implement through their personal wellness plans.
- IV. Develop awareness areas in their life where small changes can result in enhanced wellness and resiliency.
- V. Learn about the importance of diet and nutrition on wellness and resiliency.
- VI. Learn practical approaches to improving diet and nutrition.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
1300 – 1320	Land-based activity (LOA 1)	<p><i>*Email participants prior to the course:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reminder about bringing outside clothing and shoes</i> <p>Welcome students into the classroom.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orient students to the fact that we will take part in a short walk outside. Students will leave their belongings in the locked classroom. Students will be asked to bring their wellness planners on the walk along with a pen or pencil. • We will take a short walk outside through the woods. Students will be asked not to talk once we start on the trail. Rather, students will be encouraged to listen. We will stop about 2 minutes into the walk and students will be asked to find a comfortable position (standing or sitting) and breath. • Instructor will guide students through 3 cycles of breath work, then have students reflect in silence for 1 minute. • At the end of one minute, students will be asked to write down 5 things they see, 4 things they feel, 3 things they hear, 2 things they smell, 1 thing they taste, and one thing they are grateful for. • The whole group will then return to the classroom 	Walk outside and engage in grounding and mindfulness activities
1320-1330	CBC Clip to ground students to the importance of resiliency in healthcare (LOA 2)	<p>YouTube Clip (PP Slide 3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Hospital ER feels impact of a ‘system starved for years’” (9:10)</i> • <i>Students watch the video then reflect on the importance of resiliency on health care workers. The video shows how short staffed the health care system is and the reason that health care workers require resiliency training. The purpose of the timing for this video is to remind students that resiliency training can help to support their ability to sustain working within strained healthcare systems.</i> 	Reflect on the importance of resiliency for sustainability in health care
1330 - 1430	Students to work on personal wellness plan (LOA 3 & 4)	<p>Powerpoint presentation (Slides 3 - 8)</p> <p>Students responded to the time in class to prepare their personal wellness plans with gratitude. Students reported that they required a lot of clarification on the plan and on setting their SMART goals. Students required reminders to read the assignment and to prepare to answer each component. At the end of the class time to work on the project, students were advised that at this time, they would be able to write parts 1 and 2 of their personal wellness plans. Students are advised to start their implementation this week to have documentation for parts 3 and 4 of the assignment. For the SMART goal, students are advised</p>	Students work on personal wellness plans – part 1 and 2

that the written parts of the assignment are prompts, but not necessarily questions that each needed to be answered.

Most students will require feedback and guidance on their SMART goals so that they are appropriately specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time bound. Most feedback will be provided to help students identify an observable and specific goal.

Slides 7 – 8 provide direction on how students might consider language in their personal wellness plans.

1. **PERSONAL WELLNESS GOAL:** Document what you are trying to change and why (provide evidence for this choice). Include at minimum:
 - Self- assessments of all aspects of wellness, especially those related to your focus area/wellness goal. Comment on what you have learned from these assessments and how they helped you to decide on a goal.
 - Reference to readings from text, handouts or other sources that helped you to decide what to change. (Provide at least three references from class readings, reliable articles, and/or on-line health information sources)
 - Excerpts from your personal wellness journal that support your decision to try to make this change.
 - Comments on the benefits of this change.
 - Comments on the costs to yourself or others of this change (financial, time, energy, conflicting priorities etc.)
 - A statement about what you want to accomplish and why. You can use this statement as the “Specific” part of your Action Plan.
2. **ACTION PLAN:** Clear statements on how you plan to meet your wellness goal. These should be action-oriented, concrete statements. Include at minimum:
 - Specific and descriptive detail on your planned activities to meet your goal.
 1. What do I want to accomplish?
 2. Why do I want to accomplish this?
 - Measurable
 1. How will I measure my success?
 2. How will I know when this goal is accomplished?
 - Achievable
 1. How will I accomplish this goal?
 2. What are the steps needed to accomplish this?
 - Relevant
 1. Is this the right goal for me? Is this the right time?
 2. Do I have the resources I need to accomplish this goal?

		<p>3. Does this plan bring me towards my long-term wellness goals?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Time-Bound <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. When will I start and finish? (A goal date of November 4th MUST be included in this section). 2. What amount of time will I set aside regularly to accomplish your goal? (Consider creating a calendar with weekly summaries outlining your progress). ▪ Include other details such as specifics of where, when, and how you will proceed with your plan and the resources you will access. 	
1430 – 1445	Break	Nina was unable to make the Thursday class this week	
1445 - 1545	PowerPoint Presentation on Nutrition (LOA 4, 5, & 6)	<p>Presentation on Nutrition (PP Slides 7 - 13)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instructor asks the class to identify a question, a myth, a fact, anything related to nutrition (7 minutes). These get listed on the board, then the instructor can address them as the presentation unfolds. - Video on “What’s the Best Diet? Healthy Eating 101” (15:13) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fqhYBTg73fw&t=3s - This video provides a great overview of healthy eating and introduces the psychology behind sustained healthy relationships with food. The instructor may pause the presentation to further discuss any components that relate to student questions from the board. <p>Slide 10 links to Canada’s Food Guide. The instructors can walk students through the guide and show the plate and making water the drink of choice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Show students the tabs on the site to recipes, tips for healthy eating, and resources. - Slide 10 also has a link to “How sugar affects the brain - Nicole Avena” (5:02) which provides a great overview of how sugar can harm the body. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IEXBxijQREo <p>Slide 11 shows a visual example of the amount of sugar in a common Frappuccino drink. This serves to emphasize how it’s important to know the sugar content of our favorite treats so help us make better food choices.</p> <p>Slide 12 provides a link to a TedEd video on the importance of water. This video serves to help students make the informed decision to make water the drink of choice. “What would happen if you didn’t drink water? - Mia Nacamulli” (4:51). https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9iMGFqMmUFs</p> <p>Slide 13 allows for group work (if time allows). This activity typically takes a minimum of 20 minutes. On this slide there is a TedEd on how food affects the brain. This is an additional resource for students.</p>	Students list their considerations on the board. Some of these can be addressed during the class, others can have resources added through Moodle.
1545 - 1550	Survey on HCA 111	<p>PP Slide 14 – A poll Everywhere class activity</p> <p>Students provide anonymous feedback on HCA 111. This includes the content, activities, and general feedback on what</p>	

		students enjoy and what they would like to see more/less of in the course.	
1550 - 1555	Homework	Review homework	

The reflection from readings and homework was skipped from this class to allow more time for students to work on the personal wellness plan. Additionally, this class was an improvised date due to a class cancelled in response to an impromptu stat following the death of Queen Elizabeth. Having 2 reflections in one week did not feel like the most meaningful use of class time.

Some students voiced a request not to walk, so a vote was conducted in the classroom and most students wanted to go for the walk. The weather was favorable, so we conducted the walk, and it went very well. Students require ongoing reminders to bring layers to prepare for the land-based components.

Through the remaining time, I tried to keep the information on nutrition very simple. I provided general instruction on mindful eating, making water the drink of choice, and generally limiting processed and sugar filled foods. This seemed well received in the time available. I was unable to get to the group activity, but I think it should be left in for a class that does not have as much discussion.

Their survey results were very helpful. They provided validation for the land-based activity. It is very well received and enjoyed. Students generally provided feedback that they would like more participation and practical skill building time. Very positive feedback overall.

Student Feedback

HCA 111 Survey 1

What has been helpful for you so far in this course?

Response

Learning about my wellness

Extremely helpful

The reflective journals alongside the walks prior to class starting

Knowing about health and well-being

My friends and communicating with my instructors

Doing Journals

The experiences that other people share in class

Introspection

What would types of activities would you like to have in this course?

Response

I enjoy doing the mindfulness exercises where we write down our feelings and trouble

More walks and outdoor activities

Outdoor walks

More short walks

Walking, guided meditation

Circle time! To talk about who we are.

What are three things that can improve the class most?

Response

Videos, hands on, time to work on projects in class

More participation

Doing readings

Prepared

More active activities

Interactions

Fun engaging activities, more fun educational videos, and discussions

More reading materials (books)

It's great. No need for improvements

More participation

Art to express ourselves

Openess

Music or meditation sessions

What is one thing you'd change about the class if you could?

Response

Nothing

Nothing i love it just the way it is

Nothing.

Maybe a colouring exercise, class is great other than that

What else would you like to share about your experiences so far and/or any other feedback that you have to share?

Response

You're amazing!! I really like your teaching style and the way you word your quizzes

It's been a wonderful class!

nothing

I love the class and writing the journals

The class is the best, because of the people I'm with in the class and how they share their personal knowledge

HCA 111: Class 5**In-Person Oct 3, 2022, 0900 – 1200**

This class dives into the concepts of social and mental health and works to focus on the importance of these topics on resiliency and wellness.

Materials and supplies

- Course textbook (Brene Brown's Gifts of Imperfection)
- Life/Work Balance Self-Test What's Draining You

Printed Items

- Life/Work Balance Self-Test What's Draining You

- Instructor resource – van der Kolk, B. A. (2014). *The body keeps the score: Brain, mind, and body in the healing of trauma*. Viking.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- Describe how one's ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 5

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- Participate in a land-based mindfulness activity.
- develop an understanding of social and mental health for long-term resilience.
- Students will identify sources of support and sources of stress in their lives through use of the "Life/Work Balance Self-Test What's Draining You?"
- Develop awareness areas in their life where small changes can result in enhanced wellness and resiliency.
- Develop greater self-awareness through self-assessments.
- Learn practical approaches to social and mental health.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
0900 - 0915	Welcome and review of readings	<p>Prior to class email students to inform them that they will be taking part in a longer walk this week and to dress appropriately.</p> <p>Welcome and Classroom discussion regarding assigned reading and activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss the readings from Gifts of Imperfection in the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format. 	Students reflect on their readings
0915 - 0955	PowerPoint presentation on social and mental health (LOA 2, 4, & 6)	<p>Slides 1-3 review course overview. Slide 4 includes video links to introduce the topic. One of the links shows a very simple video on neuroplasticity. The purpose of this video is to visualize that humans have some control over how we react to information through strengthening of pathways within the brain that result in a practical means of managing our responses to many events. This is important in health care because workers are faced with many stressful and emotionally reactive situations. Students are asked to consider their responses to different stressful scenarios, then are asked to identify one situation that they would like to learn to react better to.</p>	Students listen to the lecture and video and offer thoughts through the presentation

		<p>Slide 5 provides a visual representation of how the brain processes information. The instructor provides verbal lecture on how information is processed in the “ancient” parts of the brain first, then progresses up to the prefrontal cortex. Students learn that often our emotional brain reacts to information before our prefrontal cortex can process what is happening. This is important to know about our brains because we can learn strategies to strengthen our processing of information and regulate the emotional responses through cognitive behavioral therapies, counselling, meditation, and a host of other approaches. As future health care providers, students need to become aware that they will need to know what their emotional responses are to difficult situations, and that they will need to work on strengthening their ability to manage those emotional responses to enhance their resiliency.</p> <p>Slide 6 – a Ted Talk from Francoise Mathiou on compassion in health care. This talk discusses the importance of self-awareness and self-care strategies on the approaches of health care providers.</p>	
0955 - 1000	Self-Assessment (LOA 3)	Slide 7 – “Life/Work Balance Self-Test What’s Draining You?” Self-assessment	Students will be introduced to activity and have 5 minutes to start it. Students are not asked to hand this in, rather it is for personal reflection.
1000 - 1015	Break	Nina joins the class	
1015 - 1025	PowerPoint presentation on social and mental health (LOA 2, 4, & 6)	<p>Slide 8 – “Your Wellness Journey”. Students are asked to consider the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – How do you rate your mental health? – Physical Health? – Social Health? – What are supports and barriers in your life for each? – Based on what we have discussed in class, what would you like to improve? 	Students read the questions and can verbalize their answers in an open group discussion.
1025 - 1050	PowerPoint presentation on social and mental health (LOA 2, 4, & 6)	<p>Slide 9 – “Good Cognitive Health”. This slide provides an overview of practical lifestyle approaches to good cognitive health. I often offer that if students don’t know where to begin with improving their mental and social wellness, that they start with working on improving their sleep and water intake (within recommended limits) and go from there.</p> <p>Slide 10 – “Physical Health – Why do we need to exercise?”. In this slide, the instructor provides information on the links between physical activity and good mental and social health. Students are encouraged to add in activity to their day on a routine basis. If students do not know where to start, I encourage them to talk about things they like that have body movement as a component. I often encourage students to consider dancing to their favorite music for 1 minute when they feel like they have no will to exercise as this promotes movement and requires very little in terms of time and preparation. Students who report having little to no activity in</p>	Students listen to the lecture and video and offer thoughts through the presentation

		<p>their life are encouraged to add in just 1 minute a day and work up from there. Students are encouraged to consider a smart approach to having an activity as part of every day to enhance the likelihood of creating a healthy habit.</p> <p>Slide 11 – “Yes, you can”. A recording of a convocation speech delivered by Steve Jobs at Stanford University. In this video, he talks about never giving up while following your passion.</p> <p>Slide 10 – A homework reminder with an addition to encourage students to call a friend or family member that they have not spoken with in a while.</p>	
1050 - 1055	Students prepare to go outside		
1055 – 1130	Land-based activity (LOA 1, 4, 6)	<p>Nina and Sam guide the students on a longer walk. Walk from the class, out to Roddy’s camp. Once there, have students sit outside. Nina guides the class through a conversation about mental and social health. Students stand in a circle for a guided meditation that lasts about 5 minutes. Following this, students are asked not to talk and to take this opportunity to tune in to their own bodies while listening to the sounds around them. Students are informed that for the remainder of the time, they should be on the lookout for an item found in nature that they feel a connection with. These items are to be loose and, on the ground, not connected to a living piece of nature. Students are guided through the woods for a 15-minute walk and be on the lookout for the item. Students are guided through the woods and return to the classroom.</p>	Walk outside and engage in grounding and mindfulness activities
1030 - 1155	Think, pair, share (LOA 1, 4, 6)	<p>Students work in groups of 3 to discuss the land-based activity and the items that they collected (10 minutes). The groups then engage in a whole-class discussion about the items and their reflections (15 minutes).</p>	Think, pair, share
1550 - 1555	Homework	Review homework and exit ticket	

http://www.compassionresiliency.com/uploads/6/8/3/6/68369495/whats_draining_you2014cr.pdf

Reflection:

This class felt a bit rushed from my perspective in terms of getting through the lecture and material. When Nina arrived, I still had some lecture to get through. She was an active participant in class and added to the discussion. She reported enjoying being a part of the lecture and having a sense of where the class was leaving off prior to the land-based component. Students reported that they enjoyed the self-assessment, and that this activity helped them to identify modifiable stressors in their life.

The time allocation for today’s land-based component exceeded previous classes. It felt wonderful to engage the class in the practical components that we were learning. We walked from the class to Roddy’s camp and stood around the fire pit (there was no fire at the time). Here, Nina guided the class through a grounding meditation and spoke with them about the importance of the land and the human connection to nature. The students stood in silence while Nina guided the students to not talk and to take this opportunity to tune in to their own bodies while listening to the sounds around them. Students are informed that for the remainder of the time, they should be on the lookout for an item found in nature that they feel a connection with. These items are to be loose and, on the ground, not connected to a living piece of nature.

I walked behind the class on our remaining walk through the woods and back to the classroom. I watched as they walked in silence and looked around for items. Some grabbed an item while walking. Others stopped and observed

before carefully selecting their piece. I enjoyed how students made space for each other and acted respectfully throughout the activity. Some students seemed deep in contemplation while others were walking quite briskly (the weather was a chilly 5 degrees and not everyone came prepared with appropriate outdoor clothing). Everyone, including Nina and myself, collected items along the walk.

We returned to the classroom and arranged students in groups for the think, pair, share activity. Students were active in their groups and had good discussions. When we brought everyone back to the larger group for the whole class discussion, I was rather surprised at how deep some of the reflections were about why students chose their item and what it represented for them. This activity was another reminder about how much students had been through during the pandemic, and their vulnerabilities. I felt honored to be a witness to their introspection and their willingness to share their reflections with the class. Nina's presence was critical in the guidance and support that she was able to offer. Each student took a turn in sharing their reflection. Each student was supported by the class.

I can't say for certain that all classes will have the same receptiveness to the land-based and reflective components. I think the HCA program does a really great job of creating a sense of community during the orientation in August. I think the early ground rules are foundational to creating a safe space in the classroom and with these practical based interventions.

HCA 111: Class 6

In-Person **Oct 17, 2022, 0900 – 1200**

This class dives into the concepts of harm reduction and works to focus on the importance of these topics on resiliency and wellness.

Materials and supplies

- Activity workbook
- Course textbook (Brene Brown's Gifts of Imperfection)

Printed Items

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one's ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 6

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Participate in land-based mindfulness activity.
- II. Develop an understanding of the concept of harm reduction and how the principle of harm reduction can enhance resilience.
- III. Introduce students to Canada's low risk drinking guidelines.
- IV. Develop awareness areas in their life where small changes can result in enhanced wellness and resiliency.
- V. Develop greater self-awareness through self-assessments.
- VI. Learn practical approaches to harm reduction on an individual and client-focused perspective.

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
0900 - 0915	Welcome and review of readings	Prior to class email students to inform them that they will be taking part in a longer walk this week and to dress appropriately.	Students reflect on their readings

		<p>Welcome and Classroom discussion regarding assigned reading and activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss the readings from Gifts of Imperfection in the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format. 	
0915 - 0920	PowerPoint presentation on harm reduction (LOA 2)	Slides 1-2 5-minute guided meditation on YouTube followed by an introduction to today's topics of harm reduction	Students listen to the lecture and video and offer thoughts through the presentation
0920 - 0940	Think, pair, share (LOA 2)	Slide 3 –“What are our barriers to change?” In Groups – please identify: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Addiction – “Safe limits” of substances – Stigma – Barriers to people getting help. – Resources for getting help. 	Students will work in groups of 3 to write down their thoughts to the questions to the left. Students are asked to write their answers on the board.
0940 - 1000	PowerPoint presentation on addiction (LOA 2)	Slide 4 – 2 videos The first video is from Gabor Mate as he discusses the connection between trauma and addiction. Provide time for a discussion following this video as it can bring a lot up for people. The instructor should work to promote discussion on how we view people with “addiction”. The second video is from “crash course psychology” on trauma and addiction.	
1000 - 1015	Break	Nina joins the class	
1015 - 1025	PowerPoint presentation on social and mental health (LOA 2, 4, & 6)	Slide 8 – “Your Wellness Journey”. Students are asked to consider the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – How do you rate your mental health? – Physical Health? – Social Health? – What are supports and barriers in your life for each? – Based on what we have discussed in class, what would you like to improve? 	Students read the questions and can verbalize their answers in an open group discussion.
1025 - 1050	PowerPoint presentation on social and mental health (LOA 2, 4, & 6)	Slide 9 – “Good Cognitive Health”. This slide provides an overview of practical lifestyle approaches to good cognitive health. I often offer that if students don't know where to begin with improving their mental and social wellness, that they start with working on improving their sleep and water intake (within recommended limits) and go from there. Slide 10 – “Physical Health – Why do we need to exercise?”. In this slide, the instructor provides information on the links between physical activity and good mental and social health. Students are encouraged to add in activity to their day on a routine basis. If students do not know where to start, I encourage them to talk about things they like that have body movement as a component. I often encourage students to consider dancing to their favorite music for 1 minute when they	Students listen to the lecture and video and offer thoughts through the presentation

		<p>feel like they have no will to exercise as this promotes movement and requires very little in terms of time and preparation. Students who report having little to no activity in their life are encouraged to add in just 1 minute a day and work up from there. Students are encouraged to consider a smart approach to having an activity as part of every day to enhance the likelihood of creating a healthy habit.</p> <p>Slide 11 – “Yes, you can”. A recording of a convocation speech delivered by Steve Jobs at Stanford University. In this video, he talks about never giving up while following your passion.</p> <p>Slide 10 – A homework reminder with an addition to encourage students to call a friend or family member that they have not spoken with in a while.</p>	
1050 - 1055	Students prepare to go outside		
1055 – 1130	Land-based activity (LOA 1, 4, 6)	<p>Nina and Sam guide the students on a longer walk. Walk from the class, out to Roddy’s camp. Once there, have students sit outside. Nina guides the class through a conversation about mental and social health. Students stand in a circle for a guided meditation that lasts about 5 minutes. Following this, students are asked not to talk and to take this opportunity to tune in to their own bodies while listening to the sounds around them. Students are informed that for the remainder of the time, they should be on the lookout for an item found in nature that they feel a connection with. These items are to be loose and, on the ground, not connected to a living piece of nature. Students are guided through the woods for a 15-minute walk and be on the lookout for the item. Students are guided through the woods and return to the classroom.</p>	Walk outside and engage in grounding and mindfulness activities.
1030 - 1155	Think, pair, share (LOA 1, 4, 6)	<p>Students work in groups of 3 to discuss the land-based activity and the items that they collected (10 minutes). The groups then engage in a whole-class discussion about the items and their reflections (15 minutes).</p>	Think, pair, share
1550 - 1555	Homework	Review homework and exit ticket.	

Reflection:

The Yukon has a very high percentage of substance use and misuse, and the student population at Yukon University is no exception. I always feel the need to be gentle when discussing harm reduction and substance use as it has the potential to have a large impact on students. I try and promote respect and a trauma informed lens when looking at issues of any substance use with the class because this subject can carry such a weight, especially for students who have a substance use disorder or who are impacted by others with a substance use disorder. The students were quiet as we worked through the modules on trauma and addiction. Students reported feeling heavy and slightly overwhelmed at this point in the term.

The time allocation for today’s land-based component exceeded previous classes. One hour was allocated for the land-based component for today’s class. It felt wonderful to engage the class in the practical components that we were learning. We walked from the class, outside for about 7 minutes to a viewpoint with a lookout over Whitehorse. At the lookout, Nina stopped the class and encouraged the students to take a few deep breaths and

absorb the beauty of the day. The walk continued to Roddy’s camp where Nina engaged the students in land-based mindfulness through a grounding ritual.

I was deeply grateful for Nina and her teachings. The students seemed to relax and settle in during the walk. Nina supported the students through the grounding activities and guided the class through a conversation about mental and social health. Students stood in a circle for a guided meditation that lasted about 5 minutes. Students were guided through the woods and returned to the classroom.

What I really appreciated was the opportunity to move these vulnerable subjects out into nature and have the support of Nina and her lived experiences and wisdom. The students all thanked her upon our return to the classroom. This class on harm reduction and addiction can be very challenging for students due to the amounts of trauma and addiction in the north. This revised format allowed for physical processing time, connection, Elder-led learning, and land-based support to give students a safe space to learn and grow.

HCA 111: Class 7

In-Person **Oct 24, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

This half-day session provides an overview of spirituality in wellness.

Materials and supplies	Printed Items
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coffee/tea, • Muffins, • Equipment for the outside fire (fire extinguisher), • Meditation singing bowl, • Table for food, • Plates and cups • Greenwood, M., de Leeuw, S., & Lindsay, N. (2018). <i>Determinants of Indigenous peoples’ health: Beyond the social</i>. (2nd ed.) Canadian Scholars. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student Handout for “Spirituality and Wellness”

Materials and supplies

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 7:

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Participate in class community-building activity through sharing food and drink with the class.
- II. Participate in land-based activity and self-reflection.
- III. Develop a deeper understanding of spirituality as a component of individual wellness.
- IV. Explore major themes of spirituality, balance, cultural safety, storytelling & traditional healing.
- V. Be introduced to the connection between cultural safety with spirituality in wellness.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
0900 – 1000	Students have 1 hour to work on PWP – rough copy due	<p><i>*Email participants prior to the course:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reminder about class starting at 1000 and that we will be spending the day conducting land-based activities, so they should be prepared for the cold weather.</i> • <i>Reminders to be sent 1 week in advance, then 3 days in advance, then the night before</i> • <i>Remind students to bring their own coffee cups.</i> <p><i>Students were also asked to prepare an “artefact” and bring this to class:</i></p> <p><i>“Artefact – you are asked to prepare to present on an “Artefact” that includes some of the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Means something to you</i> • <i>Describes who you are</i> • <i>Describes what is important to you</i> • <i>Tells us where you came from and what that means</i> • <i>Or something else deeply profound – or fun (doesn’t have to be deeply profound)</i> <p><i>It could be a photo, a memento from a special trip or time, a poem, a collage about you or your family. Whatever. . . Be prepared to tell us about it and why it represents you or your values.”</i></p> <p>Supplies required include coffee/tea, muffins, equipment for the outside fire (fire extinguisher), meditation singing bowl, table for food, plates and cups</p> <p>HANDOUTS: “Letter to Surgeon” Definitions of cultural safety and humility,</p> <p>Instructor Preparation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare the land-based location (start fires, have extinguisher on location, prepare tables and chairs, prepare coffee and tea). - Elder Nina will arrive at 10 and assist with facilitation 	Students arrive at 10am with a food item to share (group allergies include seafood, nuts, and pineapple)
1000 - 1020	Community Building (LOA 1, 5)	<p>Welcome and class initiation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students arrive and prepare their morning drink and snack • Students will reflect on the following question (Printed on the food table) • “What does spirituality have to do with wellness? Why is connection important? How can spirituality impact connection?” <p>ASK: Students to reflect on the question above</p>	Eat, drink, and discuss

1020 - 1025	Spirituality and wellness (LOA 2, 3)	<p>Spirituality and Wellness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nina and Sam will officially welcome the group students will be encouraged to listen. Students will be asked to find a comfortable position (standing or sitting) and breath. - Instructor will bang the singing bowl - Instructor will guide students through 3 cycles of breath work, then have students reflect in silence for 1 minute. - During the silence, students will be guided to consider 5 things they see, 4 things they feel, 3 things they hear, 2 things they smell, 1 thing they taste, and one thing they are grateful for. • Instructor will bang the singing bowl. Nina may have information to add and may change the activity. 	Guided breathwork and grounding
1025 - 1100	Spirituality and wellness reflection (LOA 2, 3, 4)	<p>Student led reflections on Spirituality and Wellness: Students take turns sharing about the item that they brought and the impact that it has on them</p> <p><i>Artefact – you are asked to prepare to present on an “Artefact” that includes some of the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Means something to you • Describes who you are • Describes what is important to you • Tells us where you came from and what that means • Or something else deeply profound – or fun (doesn't have to be deeply profound) <p><i>It could be a photo, a memento from a special trip or time, a poem, a collage about you or your family. Whatever. . .</i></p> <p><i>Be prepared to tell us about it and why it represents you or your values.</i></p>	
1035- 1115	Spirituality and wellness (LOA 3, 4, 5)	<p>Instructor led storytelling and activity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss spirituality in wellness • Ask group - “Think back to a time you had surgery. How did you prepare for this?” – allow time for students to share a few stories. • Tell the group that you will be reading a story written by Patricia Makokis – an internationally renowned speaker who is passionate about Indigenous health and wellness. <p>Facilitator will share a story from Greenwood, M., de Leeuw, S., & Lindsay, N. (2018). <i>Determinants of Indigenous peoples' health: Beyond the social</i>. (2nd ed.) Canadian Scholars. Ch. 21 – “From the Hospital Bed to Mother Earth”. The story from Patricia regarding her hysterectomy, how she prepared spiritually for her surgery. The information below can be included for the discussion after the story:</p>	Active listening and reflection Discission on “Think back to a time you had surgery. How did you prepare for this?” Students share a few stories.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patricia: Honoring the Body as a Cree Woman • “Having heard that some women suffer emotional turmoil and depression after having a hysterectomy, I wanted to prepare myself in ways that honored my identity as a Cree woman.” (p. 259) • Prior to surgery: women’s pipe and feast, reflection, preparation • “I felt that... I should... bring these body parts home and provide ceremony for them, and I gave this much serious thought. ... I decided to honor my life-giving uterus and ovaries by wrapping them in sage and broadcloth.” (p. 262) • Gynecologist advised to put wishes in writing; letter was sent to doctor and hospital • Entering the hospital and undergoing surgery • Chose specific clothing, said prayers, tied ribbons in hair: “I was grateful that the operating room staff was respectful of my wishes...” (p. 265) • After the surgery • Staff was engaged, respectful • Brought surgical remains home for ceremony with family <p>Cultural safety takes us beyond:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • Cultural awareness, the acknowledgement of difference. • • Cultural sensitivity, the recognition of the importance of respecting difference, and; • • Cultural competence, which focuses on the skills, knowledge, and attitudes of practitioners. <p>While these three approaches have contributed to our understanding of the need to attend to a patient’s culture, there are real limitations and concerns associated with each of them.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking a cultural safety approach to dealing with inequities enables care providers to improve health care access for patients, aggregates, and populations; acknowledge that we are all bearers of culture; expose the social, political, and historical context of health care; and interrupt unequal power relations.¹² • A central tenet of cultural safety is that it is the patient who defines what “safe service” means to them. 	
1115 - 1120	Spirituality and wellness activity (LOA 2, 5)	<p>Student Activity: Students are provided with a handout with the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imagine that you are going in for surgery. Using the concepts, we have discussed today, write a letter to your “surgeon”, or draw a picture, write a poem, a song, whatever feels right. You don’t need to imagine that anything is wrong with your body but focus on what you would want your surgeon to know about you. • What is important about who you are? How do you identify yourself? What do you love? Who do you cherish? What nourishes you? What grounds you? If 	Students are provided this activity and are asked to think about the questions while the facilitator reads the next section.

		<p>you could have one item in with you, what would it be? Why would that be important?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feel free to share this by talking or keep it for yourself. Whatever feels right. 	
1120 - 1150	Spirituality and wellness (LOA 4)	<p>Student reflection: Sam starts by reading her letter: “Thank you, my surgical team for helping to heal my body. Please know that I pride myself on my resilience, I have seemed to come back stronger from things that should have broken me down. But I am stubborn. I do not easily ask for help. I try to smile and carry my burden on my own. I seem strong and calm, but I have a fragile heart, so please be kind to my body. Be gentle whenever possible. I am a nurse, a mother of 2, a nature and travel lover, and someone with an exciting road ahead of her. I pour myself into helping others and am often not aware of my own needs. Please know that I might need to be told the limitations to allow me the time and permission to heal. I ask to bring a smooth rock with me. One the size of my palm as this has always helped to ground me and give me a sense of wholeness when I feel that I might otherwise fall apart. Finally, please know that I am so grateful to you, and everyone who is putting their needs aside to help. Please look after yourself so that you are also well. Thank you, Sam”</p> <p>Students share their thoughts and/or letters written as part of the activity</p>	Students work through the activity and either share their thoughts or continue to reflect.
11:50 – 11:55	Homework and Exit ticket	<p>Exit ticket: Reflection on the final activity</p>	

References:

Greenwood, M., de Leeuw, S., & Lindsay, N. (2018). *Determinants of Indigenous peoples' health: Beyond the social*. (2nd ed.) Canadian Scholars.

Reflection: Whitehorse had experienced a large snow the night before and the temperature was low. I was grateful for the later start to class because it took a while to prep the outdoor camp and start the fire. A few students brought food to share with the class. The Elder on campus program prepared Labrador tea for the students and brought this out. Despite the fire and the warm drinks, it was still a very chilly class. Due to the poor weather, the driving conditions were a challenge.

Nina called ahead to tell me that she would be late, so I started class without her. The class went as planned and Nina joined in around 1100. The student reflections were very impactful. All students brought an item to speak about, and I was very pleased about the respect that they each showed to whoever was speaking. I felt that having the students on the land brought out an honesty and authenticity that I often don't see in the classroom. Students spoke powerfully about how their items represented strength. For some students, it was photos of loved ones and stories about how their loved ones helped to shape who they are today. For others, it was art that represented their struggles with mental illness and their ability to find light in the darkness. There was no time limit on the sharing of each person and the time for the

activity took about 7 minutes per student. I was grateful for this activity because it helped to build on the activity that started the class about connection and spirituality. Nina arrived just as the students were finishing up their speaking.

When Nina arrived, she validated the shared experiences of the students and supported their ongoing personal development and growth. Nina highlighted how important self-care is to being able to care for others.

The class then settled in while I read a story about Patricia Makokis who is preparing for surgery. This story was chosen to highlight the significance of spirituality in wellness and the opportunity to have students reflect on their own connections to their bodies. I felt that this story was very impactful. The activity that followed the story allowed the students to build momentum on the impact of the story by having them create their own letter to an imaginary surgical team. In this letter, students would talk about what they want the team to know about them as a person, and how they would like their body to be honored during the surgery. This activity tied in nicely with the class theme and welcome questions: What does spirituality have to do with wellness? Why is connection important? How can spirituality impact connection?

Prior to leaving, the group shared final reflections. In this, many mentioned that they had never considered their spirituality as a component of their health needs. They spoke about how important it would be to have their needs honored if they were ever in care, and how this workshop changed their perspectives on how they will provide holistic care to their patients in the future.

For me, this workshop was deeply important and impactful. Teaching about the importance of spirituality as a component for wellness is a challenge because many people struggle to make the connection with their own spirituality. It was very important to have the land-based and Elder-led components for this class because it created safe spaces for vulnerability and self-reflection. The story by Patricia Makokis was essential because it showed what cultural safety could look like and highlighted the importance of self-awareness and self-advocacy. I was so proud of the students in how they honored themselves and their classmates. Nina's involvement provided meaningful perspectives and comfort for students. I plan to keep this class as land-based and Elder-led in the future.

HCA 111: Class 8

In-Person **Oct 31, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

This class provides an opportunity for students to receive information about the upcoming changes to the course as they transition from learning about personal to community wellness. Additionally, students are provided with time to work on their upcoming personal wellness plans with support from the instructor.

Materials and supplies

- Activity workbook
- Course textbook (Brene Brown's Gifts of Imperfection)

Printed Items

- None

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- Describe how one's ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 8

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- Participate in a guided meditation.
- Develop an understanding of the value of mindfulness and meditation as evidence-based stress reduction and resiliency building tools.
- Develop awareness areas in their life where small changes can result in enhanced wellness and resiliency.
- Develop further awareness of their personal self-care strategies.

- V. Have the opportunity to ask questions and receive support on their personal wellness plans.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
9:00 – 9:10 am	Introduction to guided mediation (LOA 1)	<p>Supplies required include blank paper for in-class activities.</p> <p>Welcome students into the classroom.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome students into the classroom. • Invite students to get comfortable in their seats in preparation for a 5 -minute guided mediation. Request that students put away electronic devices to prevent distraction. • Start the mediation – the instructor will model the desired participation by taking place in the activity. <p>Following the meditation, students are thanked for their participation and asked to share any reflections that are present for them.</p>	Guided mediation
9:10-10:00 am	Review of homework (LOA 2, 3, & 4)	<p>Instructor Presentation (PP Slide 3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Having the slide present helps students to remember what they need to include in their discussion.</i> <p>Classroom discussion regarding assigned reading and activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gifts of Imperfection reflections in the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format. <p><i>Students will have finished the “Gifts of Imperfection” book. This final reflection allows for an in-depth reflection on takeaways from the book and the opportunity to share with the group as a whole.</i></p>	Students will each take a turn to share their reflections and thoughts from the readings.

10:00 – 10:10 am	Review of Moodle and upcoming classes	<p>Class 8 represents a turning point from personal wellness to Community Wellness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instructor will review Moodle and point out that upcoming readings will be from electronic sources and that they will be more classically academic in nature. Students are advised that the readings are mandatory and that they will greatly enhance the ability of students to complete the final community wellness project. Students are also advised that the layout of classes will be changing moving forward and that there will be upcoming community participation. 	
10:10 – 11:55 am	LOA 5	<p>Class time to work on Personal Wellness Plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students arrive and are informed that they will have the entire class time to work on their personal wellness plans. • Instructor will review the required readings. • Instructor reviews the personal wellness plan assignment and invites questions. • Students are instructed that they may stay in the classroom and have support to work on the project or leave to work in another space. 	Students may either remain in the classroom or go somewhere else to work.

Reflection: Generally, this point in the term is intense for students. Often, I have observed that student will start to neglect their self-care around this point and I hear from students that they are starting to struggle. I find that providing the class time to work on this very important project allows some measure of stress relief. The HCA program is intense with 5 theory courses, a practical lab, and a practicum all in one semester.

I enjoyed this class because we settled into the start of the week by reviewing the lessons that students have learned so far and how this has impacted the resiliency and wellness of each student who was willing to share. The verbal feedback from the book and class was overwhelmingly positive and I was pleased to hear how students have worked to incorporate wellness into their daily lives whenever possible.

I initially thought that students were not using the allocated time to work on their wellness plans well as most left and I did not answer many questions or provide much in terms of additional guidance. However, after receiving the assignments and reviewing the work and reflection that went into them, I was pleasantly surprised at how much thought and detail went into this assignment. I think providing the time was very meaningful and I will do it again.

HCA 111: Class 9

In-Person **November 4th, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

This class introduces cultural safety and social determinants of health and works to discuss the impact of these subject on community wellness and safety within health care.

Materials and supplies

- Course and Assignment Outlines
- Activity workbook
- Course textbook (Brene Brown’s Gifts of Imperfection)

Printed Items

- Course and Assignment Outlines

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 9:

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Reflect on the assigned readings with a focus on cultural safety in health care.
- II. Develop an understanding of social determinants of health.
- III. Reflect on how social determinants of health impact the wellness of communities within the Yukon.
- IV. Determine areas where community wellness within Yukon can be improved through social determinants of health.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
9:00 – 9:05 am		Students hand in their personal wellness plans. Assignments are due at the beginning of class.	Hand in assignments (in-person or on Moodle)
9:05 - 9:20 am	Review of readings (LOA 1)	<p>Review readings “In Plain Sight” report: Pages 1 – 19. Retrieve from: https://engage.gov.bc.ca/app/uploads/sites/613/2020/11/In-Plain-Sight-Summary-Report.pdf</p> <p>Classroom discussion regarding assigned reading and activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review in the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format. 	Students will each take a turn to share their reflections and thoughts from the readings and homework assignment.

9:20-09:45 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Introduction to Social Determinants of Health (LOA 2, 3, & 4)	<p>Slides 1- 4: Introduction to Social Determinants of Health</p> <p>Slide 5: Videos Watch a video on “Health Inequalities in Canada - YouTube” (3:40) and a longer video showing the potential impacts of the social determinants of health at the level of the individual The Social Determinants of Health - YouTube (13:37). <i>The second video is a bit dated, but I have not found a better video to translate the impact of social determinants of health to the level of the individual person.</i></p>	Students offer thoughts and reflections.
9:45-10:15 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Introduction to Social Determinants of Health (LOA 2, 3, & 4)	<p>Presentation on Social Determinants of Health</p> <p>Slide 8 – Income and Income Distribution Slide 9 – Education Slide 10 – Unemployment and Job Security</p>	Students are asked to reflect on each slide and offer contributions. <i>How do each of these impacts your health? How do these social determinants of health impact our community?</i>
10:15 am	Break		
10:30-11:30 pm	PowerPoint Presentation on Introduction to Social Determinants of Health in Canada (LOA 2, 3, & 4)	<p>Presentation on Social Determinants of Health</p> <p>Slide 11 – “Early Childhood Development” – this slide has an optional link from TedEd in Whitehorse titled “How are the children?: Dr. Dennis Embry at TEDxWhitehorse” (20:36). If the class is quiet, I show it. If not, I do bring it up and I ask the class to watch it from home. It is nice for the students to watch local experts speaking about local regions. It helps to create a grounding place to relate the content to.</p> <p>Slides 12 – 16 – infographics on the impact of specific social determinants of health on the wellness of Canadians. Not all SDoH are represented.</p> <p>Slide 12 – “Inequalities in Early Childhood Development in Canada – Infographic”</p> <p>Slide 13 – 15 “Food Insecurity”</p> <p>Slide 16 – “Housing”</p>	Students are asked to reflect on each slide and offer contributions. <i>How do each of these impacts your health? How do these social determinants of health impact our community?</i>
11:30 – 11:50	PowerPoint Presentation on Introduction to Social Determinants of Health	<p>Student group activity “Problems to Possibilities”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Person A - Talk for a few minutes about something that is a stressor for you. - Person B - Craft a question that leads person A to reframe the challenge/problem into a possibility. - Switch – Person B talks, and person A listens then crafts a questions that leads person B to reframe the challenge/problem into a possibility 	Think, pair, share. Groups of 2. Students choose a social determinant of health that could be improved in our community. Person B requires

	(LOA 2, 3, & 4)	<p>- Let your “support person” know if their question was or was not helpful and why.</p> <p>The purpose of this is to have students support each other to reframe the community stressors into possibilities. This activity has been completed by the students in an earlier class on their own wellness needs. This reframe of the activity allows for the potential to use the same technique for community wellness and provide a starting discussion for the community wellness plan.</p>	<p>promoting to help them reframe the challenge into a possibility. Once each group has worked through both participants, a class reflection can take place. If the activity goes very quickly, the instructor can review the community wellness challenge assignment.</p>
11:50 – 12:00	Homework and Exit ticket	<p>Review homework:</p> <p>- <i>Go over the ebook readings from Moodle.</i></p> <p><i>Exit ticket:</i></p> <p><i>What did you learn about social determinants of health?</i></p> <p><i>What more would you like to learn?</i></p> <p><i>What is one possible community wellness need?</i></p>	

Reflection:

I find that students often struggle to understand social determinants of health. I like starting with the videos because they create a nice source of reference for the content to come. I would like to find a more interactive activity, one that creates a practical way to show what is shown during the video “[The Social Determinants of Health - YouTube \(13:37\)](#)”.

The readings from “In Plain Sight” provide a context of cultural safety that the class requires in preparation for their community experiential learning day. This document outlines racism and systemic racism in health care and provides a meaningful context for cultural safety. Up to this point, students have learned about reflection and self-awareness in terms of their own self and their needs. At this time, the instructor can guide students on the next step of self-awareness in terms of their role as a member of the health care system and the responsibilities that are embedded within their future roles. I review the document to highlight the importance of the definitions provided and to discuss that cultural safety must be the lens that we view any health act through. The goal of this class is to build on the self-awareness that students learned in classes 1-8 as a foundation of cultural safety.

HCA 111: Class 10

In-Person **November 7th, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

This class dives into the concepts of health equity and environmental health on community and individual wellness.

Materials and supplies

- PowerPoint presentation

Printed Items

- None

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.

VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 10:

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Participate in a mindfulness activity.
- II. Reflect on the assigned readings.
- III. Discuss the importance of environmental health on overall wellness.
- IV. Connect equity and social determinants of health.
- V. Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
9:00 – 9:10 am	PowerPoint presentation on harm reduction (LOA 1)	Welcome and Meditation Slides 1-2 5-minute guided meditation on YouTube followed by an introduction to today's topics	Students participate in the mediation
9:10 – 9:25 am	Welcome and review of readings (LOA 2)	Welcome and Classroom discussion regarding assigned reading and activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss the readings in the 3 (key points), 2 (new things learned), 1 (question) format • “Health and Health Care in Northern Canada”. Read pages 15 – 20, 124 – 129 (stop at “Assessing Health and Population Health), 133 (Sharing a Story) – 136. https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/yukoncollegeca/reader.action?docID=6727586&ppg=30	Students will each take a turn to share their reflections and thoughts from the readings and homework assignment.
9:25 - 9:35 am	Review of community wellness challenge assignment	Review the schedule for the next class, a full day of experiential learning through community engagement: 9-10am, Tour of Normandy Living. A new assisted living community. Students will receive a breakfast and tour where they will learn how the facility plans to function as a mini community by serving the holistic needs of seniors. 1030 - 1300, Food Bank. Students will assist with packing food hampers for Yukon communities 1430 - 1600, Naloxone Training at Yukon University. Students will learn about naloxone and receive training on intervention with suspected opioid overdoses. Students will receive naloxone kits if they want one. Then review the following layout of remaining classes: Class 11/12 – Community experiential learning day Class 13 – Full class time to work on community wellness projects Class 14 – Student presentations on community wellness projects Class 15 – Final day of class! If all goes well, we will do a wrap up of topics and finish the course with a movie and popcorn Review the Community Wellness Challenge Assignment by having the criteria on the screen. Students will be reminded that at this point, they	Students will provide thoughts and feedback and ask questions.

		should have an idea of what they would like to work on. The assignment was revised due to feedback that groups were causing undue stress within the student cohort. Because of this the assignment was revised to make it an independent project for students.	
9:35 - 10:15 am	PowerPoint Presentation on health equity (LOA 4)	<p>Slides 4-21: Introduction to health equity</p> <p>The slides for this section come from the <i>health equity resources for EPHPs, on the BCCDC website. The presentation comes with a presenter guide. The presentation was chosen because it does a wonderful job of linking equity, social determinants of health, and community wellness.</i></p>	Students offer thoughts and reflections
10:15 – 10:30	Break		
10:30-10:40 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Environmental wellness (LOA 3, 5, & 6)	<p>Presentation on Environmental Wellness</p> <p>Slide 22 – This slide asks students prompting questions on how environment impacts wellness:</p> <p><i>What is environmental wellness? How does it impact overall health? What do you need in your environment to be well? What would you like to learn more about?</i></p> <p>Instructor shows the following link on climate change and reviews the website https://climate.nasa.gov/evidence/</p>	Students write their own thoughts on the prompting questions, then a group discussion takes place.
10:40 - 11:05 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Environmental wellness (LOA 3, 5, & 6)	<p>Videos to further the discussion on environmental wellness</p> <p>Climate change: Earth’s giant game of Tetris - Joss Fong TED-Ed (2:49) and Healthy Planet, Healthy People Courtney Howard TEDxMontrealWomen - YouTube (16:04). The first video provides a general overview of the impact of climate change on the earth’s atmosphere. The second video is long, but very powerful. It does include some graphic and potentially triggering material, but it speaks about the impact of climate change and provides some meaningful and practical strategies that individuals can be a part of to mitigate the worsening of climate change.</p>	
11:05-11:30 am	PowerPoint Presentation on Environmental wellness (LOA 3, 5, & 6)	<p>Presentation on environmental wellness</p> <p>Slide 24 - 26 – Information slides speaking on one modifiable choice – single use cups. These slides indicate the harms caused and suggest that reusable items can go a long way towards reducing the impact of humans on climate change.</p>	Students are asked to reflect on each slide and offer contributions.
11:30 – 11:55	PowerPoint Presentation on Environmental wellness	<p>Presentation on environmental wellness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 27 – Introduces an example of the impacts of climate change on the health of a community by introducing “Isle de Jean Charles” from the Global Oneness project. This includes a 9-minute video that “explores the changes taking place on the island through the 	Students are asked to reflect on each slide and offer

	(LOA 3, 5, & 6)	<p>lives of two residents whose families are facing a future where rising seas, coastal erosion and storms are threatening to wash their home away.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Slide 28 – Instructor can click on the links to show the risk of coastal erosion to different places across the globe – Slide 29 Think, pair, share on the following discussion topics: – In groups of 3: <i>What do you do to keep environmentally healthy?</i> <i>Do you enjoy this activity?</i> <i>Do you think you need to do more to keep healthy?</i> <i>Why?</i> <i>Can you offer helpful idea to others in your group if they wish your input?</i> 	<p>contributions.</p> <p>Students write their own thoughts on the prompting questions, then a group discussion takes place.</p>
11:50 – 12:00	Homework and Exit ticket	<p>Review homework:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Remind students that the next class will take place in placements across the community</i> 	

Reflection:

This is a long and intense class with a lot of information. I do find that after the health equity portion, students are tired and a bit drained. I find this information very important to review though, because it can be hard to comprehend from readings alone. The portions on environmental wellness had a big impact on students and many made verbal commitments through this section within the class that they will act on reducing their impact on climate change. The Ted Talk video is very powerful because it is a physician from Yellowknife sharing her story of the impact that she has experienced related to climate change from her work in the north and in sub-Saharan Africa. The video offers practical and meaningful advice to students, and it is worth the watch.

This class act as the last theory day. After this class, students progress through to community experiential learning and project work. I felt nervous about the content that I had delivered through HCA 111 up to this time, and I hoped that I had covered everything that should have been included. Before this offering, there has not been a community experiential component, so I am hopeful that it is meaningful.

HCA 111: Class 11/12

In-Person **November 16th, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 4:00 p.m.**

This class provides community experiential learning. Learners are asked to reflect on the information that they have learned so far in HCA 111 relating to individual and community wellness, social determinants of health, and health equity. The community placements are chosen to provide variety and can vary depending on opportunities and instructor preference.

Materials and supplies

- Cell phone with internet access for email.
- Gifts and “Thank You” cards for the placements.
- Send a reminder to all placements and students about the layout of the day.

Printed Items

- None

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.

- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 11/12:

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Participate in community based experiential learnings.
- II. Reflect on the assigned readings.
- III. Develop a deeper understanding of social determinants of health.
- IV. Reflect on equity and social determinants of health within Whitehorse.
- V. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and identify needs for a healthier community.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
9:00 – 10:00 am	Community based experiential learning (LOA 1)	<p>Welcome, breakfast and tour Students meet at “Normandy Living”. This private independent senior living community opened 1 week prior to our tour date and is the only assisted living facility in the Yukon. Normandy living is an 84-suite complex. The monthly rent includes recreation, transportation, and all meals. The concept is to provide for the holistic needs of the Residents.</p> <p>Students are encouraged to reflect on how this facility can contribute to community wellness. Can they identify any barriers in seniors accessing this living accommodation? What are the benefits to the community by having this facility.</p>	Students participate activity
10:30 am – 1:00 pm	Community based experiential learning (LOA 1)	<p>Whitehorse Food Bank Students meet at the Whitehorse food bank to assist with stocking shelves and preparing Christmas Food Hampers. Students can participate to the best of their abilities. Students are reminded to pay close attention to their body mechanics during the physical portions of the activity. The Whitehorse food bank serves Whitehorse, Watson Lake, Atlin, Carcross, Mayo, Ross River, and Haines Junction. The Whitehorse Food bank is primarily a volunteer run organization with a large Territory to support. I was informed by the manager that they have seen much higher demand for their services and that the volunteer pool has declined over the past few years. Students are asked to reflect on how this service contributes to community wellness and its impact on the social determinants of health.</p>	Students will assist with stocking shelves and preparing food hampers for the communities.
1:00 – 2:30 pm		Break	
2:30 – 4:30 pm	Community based experiential learning (LOA 1)	<p>Naloxone Training at Yukon University Presentation from Lauren Hill with the Yukon Government Mental Wellness and Substance Use Services. Lauren will share a presentation on “Opioid Overdose Response” and teach students to administer naloxone in cases of suspected opioid overdose.</p>	Students will participate in the training and ask questions as needed.

	<p>From January to March of 2022, Yukon led the country in opioid related deaths with a substance use death rate of 74.4 per 100,000. https://health-infobase.canada.ca/src/doc/SRHD/Update_Deaths_2022-12.pdf</p> <p>Students will learn about naloxone and receive training on intervention with suspected opioid overdoses. Students will receive naloxone kits if they want one.</p> <p>Students are asked to reflect on how this training contributes to community wellness and potential impacts on social determinants of health.</p>	
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Reflection:

I had some difficulty in creating a community experiential learning day. I engaged with several services early to start the conversation, but aligning dates and times was a challenge. I had hoped to align this class with a Whitehorse community connects day, but the connects day did not align with the schedule course date. In the end, we participated in 3 very different experiences. Each served the community in a different way. Now that I have taken part in this day, I feel excited because there are so many options for how this day can come together. I felt the naloxone training was essential. Yukon leads the country in opioid related deaths, so I am passionate about more people having training on intervention. The presenter did a beautiful job of presenting the information in a way that de-stigmatizes drug use. The students responded very well to the training even though it was at the end of a long day.

Students were very moved and energized by the time at the food bank. While we were there, the food bank had a huge delivery of frozen turkeys. With the class full of young and strong students, we were able to provide some much-appreciated assistance in moving these large and heavy turkeys from the truck to the freezer. Most volunteers are senior women, so it was nice to be of value while learning. When we arrived, I let the manager take over and move the students into teams of shelve stocking or portioning out foods. It did not take long for the students to become very engaged and helpful. Everyone worked well and reported feeling very good when we left.

The breakfast and tour of Normandy was nice, and more valuable than I thought it would be. During our tour, the attendant spoke about the mission and values of the building and how they strive to create a space that promotes the highest quality of life. Following the tour, the class had a great discussion on private assisted living and the impacts that this can have on a community.

In reflection on this day, I think that the students learned WAY more from this day than they would have in the classroom. I will certainly do this again and I may try and have one more class of community experiential learning.

Food Bank Society of Whitehorse

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It's Thankful Thursday and I'd like to send out a big THANK YOU to the students from the Yukon University Health Care Assistant Program, who came to help us portion out food and stock shelves last week, and got roped into unloading 3 pallets of frozen turkeys! This crew were absolute champs and good sports about the unexpected work, and we're so thankful for their help.

If you'd like to volunteer in a group from a school, university, or workplace, we would be happy to have you. Though hopefully with less back-straining work than shifting frozen turkeys!

[#communityhelpingcommunity](#)

HCA 111: Class 13

In-Person November 21st, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.

This class provides an opportunity for students to review the final project, the “Community Wellness Challenge” and have class time to work on this project.

Materials and supplies

Printed Items

- “Self-awareness: A tool for providing culturally competent care”

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 13:

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Review the document titled “Self-awareness: A tool for providing culturally competent care” and learn how to apply this to their projects on their community wellness challenge projects.
- II. Review the requirements for the community wellness challenge assignment.
- III. Receive class time with instructor support to work on their community wellness projects.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
9:00 – 9:30 am	Review of readings (LOA 1)	<p>Welcome and review of readings. Review the readings. Focus on the “Self-awareness: A tool for providing culturally competent care” as the final assignment has a portion that will require students to reflect on the CULTURE acronym. Self-awareness: A tool for providing culturally competent care. Read the entire article. Retrieve from: https://oce-ovid-com.yukonu.idm.oclc.org/article/00152193-202002000-00016/HTML Read the “Point in time” survey page 7-24 https://yawc.ca/downloads/whitehorse-point-in-time-count-pit-2021.pdf</p>	Students reflect on the readings and can ask clarifying questions.
9:30 – 10:00 am	Review of the Community Wellness Challenge assignment (LOA 2)	<p>Review the Community Wellness Challenge by having the criteria on the screen and reviewing the content. I tend to focus on the assignment requirements of the social determinants of health and I review appropriate references and citing with the students.</p>	Students listen to the assignment criteria and ask questions.
10:00 – 12:00	Students have free time to work on their assignment (LOA 3)	Students are informed that they have the remaining 2 hours of class time to work on their final assignment. They are allowed to stay in the room or leave. They do not need to return to finish the class time. I remain available for questions and/or support.	

Reflection:

I took the time in the morning to stress the importance of including good information in the final assignment. Prior to this assignment, most of the writing in this class is reflective and does not require good references and citing. Because of this, I review the minimum number of appropriate references required and review what a “good” source is. Students responded positively to having the opportunity to review the assignment and have class time to work. Most students did not utilize having me to support them.

HCA 111: Class 14

In-Person **November 23rd, 2022, 1:00 p.m. – 4:00 p.m.**

This class provides an opportunity for students to review the final project, the “Community Wellness Challenge” and have class time to work on this project.

Materials and supplies

Printed Items

- “Community Wellness Challenge” marking forms

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 14:

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- VII. Present their community wellness challenges to the class.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
1:00 – 4:00 pm	Community Wellness Challenge presentations (LOA 1)	Community Wellness Challenge Presentations	Student’s present

Reflection:

Student’s each took turns presenting on their community wellness challenge presentations, then answered questions from the class. Several students described that the assignment had profound impacts on their worldview and how they view themselves in relation to their community.

Following the community class and the time at the food bank, several students completed their assignment on food insecurity in the North. One student was so moved from his experience at the food bank, that he initiated a food drive and arranged for food bank volunteers through his social media platform. During his presentation, he became emotional about how the project made him deeply grateful about his own access to food and how passionate that he is now about helping to feed those with food insecurity.

Another student did her project on affordable housing in the territory. She researched housing programs that run in Scandinavian countries and compared those programs with the impact that they have had on social determinants of health in their respective countries. During the questioning period of the presentation, she described that when she started the project, she felt like affordable housing was an impossible project. By the end of her project, she was so

passionate about the potential of bringing meaningful affordable housing to the territory that she reported that she would like to run for local government in the next few years to create positive change in her community. I felt very emotional during these presentations. Only one student in the class is originally from the Territory. All the others have moved from other parts of Canada (2 of nine), or international locations (3 of 9). I felt honored to witness the students view Whitehorse as their own and take active steps to promoting the health and wellness of our community. I did not know that this project was so impactful to the students, so I was overcome with joy and respect for each of the students during their presentations because they transformed their understanding of community wellness and took ownership towards translating this into making their current community better. I have never seen a class transform their learning into positive action.

I have had this assignment in previous course offerings, but I have never seen it have such an impact. Many of the students relayed their passion for the project to the community experiential day. I wonder if the impact of Nina and the land-based teaching provided the foundation of ownership and respect of community to the students.

The community wellness assignment had an individual reflection on the CULTURE acronym where students were required to use the information on self-awareness that they developed through classes 1-8 as a foundation of how they interact with other cultures. The students reflected on their own cultures and how they would like to interact with people from different cultures. Students provided self-reflection on how their culture impacts their lives and how understanding cultures that are different from their own can impact care. I was pleased with the self-reflections and self-awareness on students in relation to their own culture and in relation to the cultural safety of others. I hope that by starting with self-awareness and self-reflection, students will be able to deepen their understanding on cultural safety and learn culturally safe caregiving approaches.

HCA 111: Class 15

In-Person **Nov 28th, 2022, 9:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

This half-day session provides a final wrap-up class on personal and community wellness for Health Care Assistant Students.

Materials and supplies

- Activity workbook
- Video for the class – Link to Netflix’s “Social Dilemma”
- Popcorn
- Coffee/Tea

Printed Items

- Course and Assignment Outlines
- Wellness Wheel Self-assessment
- 3 cards with envelopes per student

LEARNING OUTCOMES for HCA 111

Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.
- V. Describe how one’s choices affect one’s environment and how the environment influences one’s health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community and plan a strategy for a healthier community.

LEARNING OUTCOMES for Class 15

Upon completion of the class, students will:

- I. Explain the interrelationship of physical, social, cognitive, emotional and spiritual determinants of health and their relationship to lifestyle choices.
- II. Identify aspects of the HCA role which could lead to unhealthy stress and how to mitigate stress.
- III. Describe how one’s ability to think, reason, interpret, remember, assess, and solve problems is related to health.
- IV. Describe the complexity of the change process in relation to health promotion, including the effects of social, cultural and spiritual components on choices and behaviors.

- V. Describe how one's choices affect one's environment and how the environment influences one's health and lifestyle choices.
- VI. Discuss factors affecting health in the community.

COURSE PLAN

Time	Topic & Learning Outcome	Learning Activity	Student Activities
0900 – 0910	Review of health and wellness (LOA 1 – 6)	<p><i>*Email participants prior to the course:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reminder that students can bring comfortable clothing and a movie snack to the last class. Remind students to bring their own coffee cups. <p>Supplies required include coffee/tea, popcorn, table for food, plates and cups</p> <p>HANDOUTS: “Wellness Wheel” self-assessment</p> <p>PowerPoint Presentation Slides 1-10 on Health and Wellness review (slides 2/3), dimensions of health review (slides 4-10).</p>	Students arrive at 0900 with a food item to share (group allergies include seafood, nuts, and pineapple)
0910 - 0930	Wellness Wheel activity	<p>Wellness Wheel Activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students will complete the wellness wheel activity and compare it with the activity that they completed on the first day of class <p>ASK: Students to reflect on their wellness wheels and how they feel about this wheel compared to the once completed on the first day of class</p>	Students will complete the wellness wheel activity and compare it with the activity that they completed on the first day of class then engage in a class discussion
0930 - 0940	Goals for the future activity	<p>Goals for the future activity: Give each student three cards with envelopes and instruct the students to do the following: <i>Based on your assessment:</i> <i>Write a note to yourself about your hopes for the future in</i> <i>6 months</i> <i>1 year</i> <i>5 years</i></p> <p>Students will write the date on the outside of each envelope and seal them.</p>	Students will complete the activity. There is no rush to complete it, so inform students that if they need more time, they can continue to work as the class continues.
0940 - 1000	Review of health and wellness (LOA 1 – 6)	<p>PowerPoint Presentation: Slides 14 - 16 on Social Determinants of Health review and slides 17 – 23 on various other topics covered in the class.</p>	
1000 - 1015	Spirituality and wellness (LOA 3)	<p>Video: Ted Talk on everyday leadership by Drew Dudley (6:01) available at Drew Dudley: Everyday leadership TED Talk</p>	Students watch the video then engage in reflection on how they may have had positive influences on others.

1015 - 1025	Break	Students can gather their movie snacks and get comfortable for the movie	
1025 - 1200	Video	Video: Students watch the video “The Social Dilemma” as a group over Netflix (1h 34m)	Students offer thoughts and reflections.

Reflection:

The final class day was great. The student reflection on the wellness wheel activity was interesting and students reported on their growth through the course. Students spoke to personal growth and resilience through the course and improvements that were documented into their wellness wheel. It was really nice to hear their perspectives about how the initial assessments on the wellness wheel impacted how they lived their lives and how the course resulted in more self-awareness.

The video was quite impactful. One student reported during the video that she was deleting her social media in that moment. The movie took up the remainder of class time. It was pleased with the impact of the video on the students, especially since they are a younger group than previous years. Most students reported that social media use was frequent for them, and that the video impacted how they wanted to continue using these platforms.

Appendix C

Wellness Wheel Self-Assessment

Walking Your Inner Circle YOUR Wellness Wheel

Wellness is a balance of many factors. Using the circle below, shade your level of satisfaction in each area of your life. Use the considerations on the next page to determine your satisfaction in your physical, spiritual, emotional and mental health and wellness.

For example, if you are 60% satisfied in your career, shade the first six levels of the career slice. Do the same for each area, starting from the center point radiating outward.

